

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles

BRIDGING THE GAP:
INCREASING EVIDENCE-BASED PRACTICE UTILIZATION
AMONG EXPERIENCED NURSES

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

Sandra Lynne Hall

Doctoral Project Committee Approval:

Kathleen Hinoki, PhD, MSN, RN, CNS, Project Chair
Jean O'Neil, DNP, RN, FNP-BC, Committee Member

May, 2019

Copyright Sandra Lynne Hall 2019 ©

ABSTRACT

Evidence demonstrates that nurse engagement in evidence-based practice (EBP) results in improved patient outcomes and increased nurse satisfaction, yet many health care organizations struggle to support nurse participation in this work. A review of literature demonstrated that major barriers to EBP engagement include lack of time, EBP knowledge, and resources such as online databases, librarian assistance, and mentorship. The purpose of this project is to develop a one-year EBP Fellowship program for experienced nurses at an urban pediatric hospital. A curriculum was developed based on evidence and organizational needs, and program guidelines, outcomes, application, and budget were developed to support program implementation. Outcomes to be measured will include number of completed EBP projects, as well as change over time in EBP knowledge and self-efficacy.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT.....	iii
LIST OF TABLES.....	vi
LIST OF FIGURES	vii
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	viii
BACKGROUND	1
Purpose Statement.....	3
Supporting Framework	3
REVIEW OF LITERATURE	7
Overview.....	7
Significance and Benefits of EBP.....	7
Barriers to EBP Utilization Among Nurses.....	8
Facilitators for EBP Utilization Among Nurses	9
Methods of EBP Education.....	10
Examples of EBP Fellowship Programs.....	10
Program Length and Time Commitment.....	10
Application Process and Participant Selection	11
Program Components	12
Program Outcomes	12
Measurement of EBP Education Outcomes.....	13
Conclusion	14
METHODS	15
Setting.....	15
Sample	15
Ethical Issues	16
Program Development and Timeline.....	16
Evaluation Methods	17

RESULTS	18
Curriculum	18
Program Components	19
IMPLEMENTATION PLAN	21
Timeline	21
Budget	21
ANTICIPATED RESULTS.....	22
Participation	22
Outcomes	22
Challenges.....	23
DISCUSSION.....	24
REFERENCES	25
APPENDIX A: PERMISSION TO USE THE JOHNS HOPKINS NURSING EVIDENCE-BASED PRACTICE MODEL.....	32
APPENDIX B: TABLES OF EVIDENCE	33
APPENDIX C: EKAN TOOL SIGNED TERMS OF USE	56
APPENDIX D: EKAN TOOL.....	58
APPENDIX E: PERMISSION TO USE EBPSE SCALE	62
APPENDIX F: EBPSE SCALE.....	63
APPENDIX G: EBP FELLOWSHIP PROGRAM CURRICULUM.....	64
APPENDIX H: EBP FELLOWSHIP CURRICULUM OUTCOMES.....	67
APPENDIX I: EBP FELLOWSHIP PROGRAM GUIDELINES.....	73
APPENDIX J: EBP FELLOWSHIP APPLICATION	74
APPENDIX K: EBP FELLOWSHIP APPLICATION SCORING RUBRIC.....	75
APPENDIX L: EBP FELLOWSHIP PROJECT PROGRESS REPORT	76

LIST OF TABLES

<u>Table</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. Significance and Benefits of EBP.....	41
2. Barriers and Facilitators for EBP Utilization Among Nurses.....	43
3. Methods of EBP Education.....	51
4. Examples of EBP Fellowship Programs.....	54
5. EBP Education Outcome Measurement	62

LIST OF FIGURES

<u>Figure</u>	<u>Page</u>
1. The Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence-Based Practice Model	12
2. The Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence-Based Practice PET Process	13

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The last few years have certainly been a journey. I owe special thanks to my project team lead, Dr. Kathy Hinoki, and my committee member Dr. Jean O'Neil. Thank you both so much for your guidance and support throughout this process. Many thanks also to the amazing faculty of the California State University DNP program. I will be forever grateful for this experience and for your support. I also want to thank the amazing leaders and colleagues who have supported me in my education, including Suzanne Taylor, Jenni Baird, Rita Secola, Mary Dee Hacker, and Nancy Lee. Sincere thanks also to Melissa Thompkins, Erika Modoyan, and Stephanie Brady for their never-ending support and kindness. I'm also incredibly thankful for my Children's Hospital Los Angeles DNP classmates, Diane Altounji, Dolores Greenwood, and Ruth Paul, who have laughed and cried with me through every step of this adventure. Marcel Proust once wrote "Let us be grateful to the people who make us happy; they are the charming gardeners who make our souls blossom." My garden is in full bloom thanks to my amazing friends, Matt Zion, Vanessa Gedney, Leigh Redman, Tim Redman, Amy Reisenbach, Brent Berneking, Krista Smith, David Zack, and Eric Shelley. I couldn't have done it without your love and support. Lastly, I am forever thankful for the support of my mother, Wanda Hall, who has shouldered her fair share of stress on my behalf over the last few decades. I am so blessed to be your daughter and hope every day to make you proud.

BACKGROUND

Evidence-based practice (EBP) is defined as “a problem-solving approach using current best evidence to answer a clinical question incorporating one’s own clinical expertise and patient values and preferences” (Melnyk & Fineout-Overholt, 2005). It has, in fact, been identified as a core competency for all health care professionals (Institute of Medicine, 2003). While the implementation of EBP improves patient outcomes and satisfaction with care (Heater, Becker, & Olson, 1988), inconsistencies in implementing EBP exist among nurses nationwide (Melnyk, Fineout-Overholt, Gallagher-Ford, & Kaplan, 2012).

Pravikoff, Tanner, and Pierce (2005) suggest that knowledge deficit about EBP is one of the most frequently reported barriers to implementing it and that nurses’ knowledge and skills in EBP directly correlate to their confidence in using evidence to guide their practice (Saunders, Stevens, & Vehvilainen-Julkunen, 2016). Therefore, increasing nurses’ knowledge about EBP and how to integrate evidence into practice may increase their participation in EBP activities. Some health care organizations have found success in providing extended training programs, called EBP Fellowships or EBP Scholars programs. Research shows that participation in such programs increases nurses’ EBP knowledge and willingness to engage in EBP efforts (Balakas, Sparks, Steurer, & Bryant, 2013).

At Children’s Hospital Los Angeles (CHLA), leaders and educators made the establishment of a culture of inquiry amongst its nursing staff a priority five years ago. The Johns Hopkins Nursing Model of Evidence-Based Practice was adopted by the organization in 2013, and efforts to increase EBP utilization have been ongoing ever

since. Evidence-based practice education has been noted to have the most success through its use in CHLA's Registered Nurse (RN) Residency Program. During this 22-week program, new graduate nurses are guided through the EBP process. They learn the fundamentals of EBP, develop a practice question, conduct a literature search, critically appraise evidence, and synthesize research findings to identify best practices.

To date, over 300 new nurses have participated in EBP projects through the RN Residency Program. Post-residency surveys indicate that after completing their project, 96.7% of new graduate nurses have sustained a strong interest in participating in EBP activities or projects. Projects completed through the RN Residency have led to several practice changes at CHLA, including new methods of nursing care for oncology patients with oral mucositis, an updated policy for securing endotracheal tubes in neonates, and the creation of a new protocol for placing intubated patients with acute respiratory distress syndrome in the prone position for optimal outcomes. Outcomes of these projects have included reduced incidence of mucosal barrier injury-related bloodstream infections, fewer accidental extubations in infants, and reduced length of stay for some critical care patients; each of these outcomes has demonstrated potential to substantially reduce health care costs.

While these EBP projects have resulted in best practices in nursing, it is important to note that many of the long-term nursing staff were hired before EBP was incorporated into the RN Residency curriculum. Thus, most nurses who have worked at CHLA for greater than four years have had limited EBP learning opportunities. Sporadic one and two-day continuing education events have been held to provide nurses with an overview

of the EBP process, but no support exists to facilitate ongoing EBP knowledge and skill development.

According to the organization's Clinical Services Research and EBP Database, only five EBP projects have been completed by nurses outside of the RN Residency Program since 2014 (Children's Hospital Los Angeles, 2018), as compared to the 148 projects produced by RN residents within that same time frame. The creation of an EBP Fellowship for more experienced nurses would provide them with the necessary education and support with the evidence-based practice process, so that they in turn will also be able to contribute towards the improvement of patient care practices at CHLA in higher numbers.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project is to develop a one-year EBP Fellowship Program for nurses at CHLA.

Objectives of this project include the following:

- Develop a curriculum for the EBP Fellowship didactic course.
- Establish program logistical procedures, including application process, class frequency, budget, and guidelines for participants.
- Design outcome measures that objectively assess nurses' EBP knowledge and perceived EBP self-efficacy before and after participation in the EBP Fellowship Program, and set up a method for monitoring the program's effect on long-term EBP utilization in practice.

Supporting Framework

Successful development of EBP education requires integration of inquiry with opportunities for learning and subsequent application into practice. These three components are crucial to building a culture of EBP in an organization (Dang & Dearholt, 2017). The recently redesigned Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence-Based Practice Model, hereafter referred to as the JHNEBP Model (Figure 1), provides a framework for this project. The JHNEBP Model was chosen because it emphasizes the interrelated nature of inquiry, practice, and learning as drivers for best practice and practice improvements. This model not only highlights the principles upon which EBP education should be based, but also provides the tools and processes that will comprise the curriculum for the EBP Fellowship Program.

Figure 1. The Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence-Based Practice Model. See Appendix A for permission to use this model.

The JHNEBP Model has been successfully used to guide many EBP projects, mostly in the clinical setting. Projects utilizing the model have led to practice changes in discharge teaching (Wood et al., 2017), reduction of post-operative infections (Mori, 2015), and community health initiatives (Wang, Mark, Braginsky, & Katz, 2017). While much of the work guided by the model thus far has led to clinical applications, the model has the potential to provide guidance for a wide range of clinical and non-clinical evidence-based inquiry.

The foundation of this project will be the JHNEBP phased approach to EBP known as PET: practice question, evidence, and translation (Figure 2). This approach ensures that inquiry, in the form of a practice question, serves as the foundation for evidence; and the appraisal and synthesis of evidence, in turn, serve as the driver for translation. These three phases will serve as the framework to guide this project. The practice question for the project is whether clinical nurse participation in an EBP Fellowship Program will result in increased EBP knowledge and self-efficacy, and ultimately lead to increased utilization of EBP in clinical practice. The JHNEBP process places an emphasis on utilizing research and non-research evidence from both internal and external sources (Dang & Dearholt, 2017). Evidence for this project includes internal data from CHLA, research, expert opinion, case reports, and program evaluations. A thorough appraisal of evidence then leads to the translation phase, in which a practice change is recommended and initiated (Dang & Dearholt, 2017). For the purposes of this project, the practice change will be the creation of an EBP Fellowship Program.

Figure 2. The Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence-Based Practice PET Process. See Appendix A for permission to use this model.

The JHNEBP Model and Process will also serve as the foundation for the EBP Fellowship Program’s curriculum, as this model is used by CHLA for all EBP projects and inquiries. The PET process can be further broken down into 19 individual steps to guide the nurse through an EBP project from beginning to end (Dang & Dearholt, 2017). These steps range from starting a project by recruiting an interprofessional team and all the way to the final step of disseminating project results. The steps will serve as guidance for the development of each component of this curriculum.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

A literature review was conducted using PubMed, CINAHL, Ovid, Web of Science, and ProQuest databases. Search terms included evidence-based practice, research utilization, hospital, nurse, education, barriers, fellowship, and internship. The search was limited to peer-reviewed articles published in English between January 2007 and April 2018. Secondary sources were derived from references identified in the primary search, including two classic studies from 1988 and 2000. A total of 53 articles were retrieved for appraisal, with a resulting 38 articles related to significance of EBP, barriers to EBP utilization, facilitators for EBP utilization, EBP education methodologies, EBP fellowship program examples, and EBP outcomes measurement, which were then subsequently selected for inclusion in the review of literature. Tables of evidence are located in Appendix B.

Significance and Benefits of EBP

Evidence demonstrated that EBP was beneficial to patients, nurses, and health care organizations; yet it is currently underutilized. A systematic review found that use of evidence-based nursing interventions resulted in a 28% improvement in patient outcomes over standard procedural nursing care (Heater et al., 1988). Hospitals have utilized EBP to increase safety and decrease variations in care, ultimately positioning themselves as high reliability health care organizations (Melnyk, 2012). Additionally, nurses who engaged in EBP might have benefitted from the experience. Research demonstrated a positive correlation between nurses' beliefs about EBP and their job satisfaction and sense of group cohesion (Melnyk, Fineout-Overholt, Giggelman, & Cruz, 2010).

According to Balas and Boren (2000), a disconnect exists between the generation of knowledge and its eventual translation into practice, with an average gap of 17 years between study publication and recognition as standard of practice. With databases and evidence readily available through the internet, this gap is of great concern. Underutilization of EBP is likely due to the many barriers that were identified in the literature.

Barriers to EBP Utilization Among Nurses

Given the significance of EBP utilization and the benefits it offers to patients, nurses, and health care organizations, one must consider the factors preventing widespread use of EBP in nursing practice. The most frequently reported barrier to EBP engagement was insufficient knowledge and skills in research and EBP (Brown et al., 2010; Brown, Wickline, Ecoff, & Glaser, 2009; Cadmus et al., 2008; Chummun & Tiran, 2008; Eizenberg, 2011; Pravikoff et al., 2005). A second frequently reported barrier to nurse engagement in EBP was a lack of time (Brown et al., 2010; Brown et al., 2009; Cadmus et al., 2008; Chummun & Tiran, 2008; Gale & Schaffer, 2009). This was characterized by not only nurses' perceived lack of time for research searching, appraisal, and change implementation (Brown et al., 2010), but also the lack of adequate staffing that would have allowed nurses to have dedicated EBP work time (Gale & Schaffer, 2009).

Another frequently reported barrier was lack of organizational support for EBP (Cadmus et al., 2008; Chummun & Tiran, 2008; Eizenberg, 2011). This manifested as a lack of support from executives and managers (Chummun & Tiran, 2008; Eizenberg, 2011), and no designated financial support for EBP efforts (Cadmus et al., 2008). From

an organizational standpoint, nurses also reported a lack of support for EBP in the form of resources, such as computers and internet access (Eizenberg, 2011; Pravikoff et al., 2005), health sciences libraries and research databases (Cadmus et al., 2008; Pravikoff et al., 2005; Yoder et al., 2014), and lack of general EBP tools and resources (Cadmus et al., 2008; Gale & Schaffer, 2009). Additional reported barriers included lack of value for research and EBP (Pravikoff et al., 2005; Prior, Wilkinson, & Neville, 2010) and the perception that nurses lack the authority to implement change (Brown et al., 2009). Taken altogether, the literature identified six major barriers: lack of knowledge, time, support, resources, value for EBP, and perceived authority. Despite these barriers, some nurses have managed to implement EBP into their workplaces.

Facilitators for EBP Utilization Among Nurses

Researchers also focused on factors which served as facilitators for EBP engagement. These included mentorship (Melnyk et al., 2012; Melnyk et al., 2018; Pravikoff et al., 2005; Prior et al., 2010; Saunders et al., 2016), access to health sciences libraries, databases, and librarians (Eizenberg, 2011; Yoder et al., 2014), computer and internet access (Eizenberg, 2011), organizational prioritization and support of EBP (Chummun & Tiran, 2008; Yoder et al., 2014), tools to assist with the EBP process (Melnyk et al., 2012), and journal clubs (Prior et al., 2010). However, the most frequently reported facilitator for nurse engagement in EBP was education to build the skills and knowledge needed for each step of the EBP process (Eizenberg, 2011; Melnyk et al., 2012; Melnyk et al., 2018; Pravikoff et al., 2005; Prior et al., 2010; Saunders et al., 2016). Several strategies for educating nurses have been reported in the literature.

Methods of EBP Education

Evidence suggests that a variety of educational activities are needed in order to build a robust culture of EBP in a health care organization (Barnsteiner, Reeder, Palma, Preston, & Walton, 2010; Bissett, Cvach, & White, 2016; Moore, 2017). Bissett et al. (2016) conducted a quality improvement project in which web-based learning, interactive classes, and EBP newsletters were included in an EBP education bundle which resulted in greater than 20% improvement in each of 44 organizational EBP competencies. However, other research findings indicate that web-based training modules may not be as effective as in-person education (Hines, Ramsbotham, & Coyer, 2015; Moore, 2017). EBP is a complicated process that requires a great deal of knowledge and skill; learner engagement is necessary to ensure transfer of knowledge and skill acquisition (Malik, McKenna, & Griffiths, 2017). One of the most effective methods of EBP education noted was a long-term education program, commonly called a fellowship, internship, or scholars program (Balakas et al., 2013; Barnsteiner et al., 2010; Bissett et al., 2016).

Examples of EBP Fellowship Programs

A number of EBP fellowship programs exist in the U.S., with many having been described in the literature. Reports of these programs revealed some similarities and differences, but all highlighted best practices. Comparisons of these EBP fellowship programs focused on program length, time commitment, application process, program components, and program outcomes.

Program Length and Time Commitment

Length of fellowship programs varied widely, with programs lasting as little as six weeks (Steurer, 2010) and as long as two years (Bartlett & Allen, 2013; Wells, Free,

& Adams, 2007). The majority of programs, however, were structured as either nine-month (Kim, Ecoff, et al., 2017; Kim, Stichler, Ecoff, Gallo, & Davidson, 2017; Selig & Lewanowicz, 2008; Weeks, Moore, & Allender, 2011) or one-year fellowships (Christenbery, Williamson, Sandlin, & Wells, 2016; Gattuso et al., 2007; Gawlinski & Becker, 2012). A majority of programs included the completion of an EBP project as part of the fellowship and combined didactic classes with independent work time (Bartlett & Allen, 2013; Christenbery et al., 2016; Gattuso et al., 2007; Gawlinski & Becker, 2012; Hockenberry, Brown, Walden, & Barrera, 2009; Kim, Ecoff, et al., 2017; Milne, Krishnasamy, Johnston, & Aranda, 2007; Selig & Lewanowicz, 2008; Weeks et al., 2011; Wells et al., 2007). Time commitments ranged from seven (Bartlett & Allen, 2013) to 20 hours per month (Gawlinski & Becker, 2012).

Application Process and Participant Selection

Eligibility for participation in EBP fellowships varied by organization. Some programs required a minimum length of employment that ranged from one year to 18 months in order to qualify for the program (Gattuso et al., 2007; Selig & Lewanowicz, 2008; Steurer, 2010). Acceptance to many programs was based on an application (Bartlett & Allen, 2013; Gattuso et al., 2007; Gawlinski & Becker, 2012), with some requiring essays (Gattuso et al., 2007), interviews (Bartlett & Allen, 2013), or a statement of support from the applicant's manager or director (Gattuso et al., 2007; Gawlinski & Becker, 2012; Selig & Lewanowicz, 2008). Participant selection was conducted by program faculty (Bartlett & Allen, 2013; Gattuso et al., 2007; Selig & Lewanowicz, 2008) or by a Nursing Research Council (Bartlett & Allen, 2013). Some programs expanded beyond nursing and included participants from other clinical professions, such

as occupational therapy, clinical nutrition, social work, and respiratory therapy (Bartlett & Allen, 2013; Milne et al., 2007; Selig & Lewanowicz, 2008).

Program Components

Didactic curricula for EBP fellowships was geared toward the steps of EBP and the skills needed to incorporate research into practice. Topics such as developing a PICO question, searching for evidence, appraising and synthesizing evidence, and implementing change were frequently incorporated into program curricula (Gattuso et al., 2007; Gawlinski & Becker, 2012; Hockenberry et al., 2009; Kim, Ecoff, et al., 2017; Milne et al., 2007; Pipe et al., 2009; Selig & Lewanowicz, 2008; Steurer, 2010; Weeks et al., 2011; Wells et al., 2007). Additional topics in some of these curricula included outcome evaluation (Gawlinski & Becker, 2012; Pipe et al., 2009; Steurer, 2010; Wells et al., 2007), abstract writing, writing for publication, poster creation, and presentation skills (Gattuso et al., 2007; Milne et al., 2007; Wells et al., 2007). Several programs also culminated with project presentations for internal dissemination (Christenbery et al., 2016; Gattuso et al., 2007; Hockenberry et al., 2009).

Program Outcomes

Measurement of outcomes varied by program, with many failing to report any substantive data to demonstrate the success of their program. Some programs identified positive program outcomes such as number of participants completing the program, number of completed EBP projects, past participants who have enrolled in higher education, Magnet exemplars, conference presentations, and manuscripts published (Bartlett & Allen, 2013; Milne et al., 2007; Wells et al., 2007). Other programs reported qualitative outcomes, such as learners reporting an increased sense of empowerment, or

increase in knowledge (Christenbery et al., 2016; Steurer, 2010). One program reported class evaluations for each didactic component of the fellowship (Bartlett & Allen, 2013). Researchers at one hospital conducted multiple studies to determine the efficacy of their EBP Fellowship Program. Results demonstrated a statistically significant improvement in EBP beliefs ($p < 0.001$), EBP implementation ($p < 0.001$), job satisfaction ($p < 0.047$), and group cohesion ($p < 0.014$) (Kim, Ecoff, et al., 2017). A six-month follow-up survey from this program found a positive correlation between a nurse's beliefs about and adoption of EBP into the work setting ($p = 0.013$).

Measurement of EBP Education Outcomes

When planning any educational initiative in a hospital setting, it is imperative to plan for the measurement of outcomes to ensure that the program's objectives are successfully met and to secure ongoing organizational support and funding (Taylor & Hall, 2017). A number of instruments for measuring both subjective and objective EBP outcomes currently exist. Subjective tools include the Self-Efficacy in EBP (SE-EBP) scale, Outcome Expectancy for EBP (OE-EBP), EBP Questionnaire (EBPQ), and the EBP Self-Efficacy (EBPSE) scale. Each of these valid and reliable scales measures learners' perceptions, attitudes, and beliefs about their ability to participate in EBP (Chang & Crowe, 2011; Tucker, Olson, & Frusti, 2009).

The EBP Knowledge Assessment in Nursing (EKAN) tool is a valid and reliable instrument designed to assess objective knowledge related to EBP (Wonder et al., 2017). While objective data allows measurement of actual knowledge transfer, subjective data remains important, as evidence demonstrates that nurses' EBP confidence levels positively correlate to their likelihood of implementing EBP in practice (Saunders et al.,

2016). However, Wonder et al. (2017) found a weak correlation between nurses' EBP knowledge and their attitudes toward EBP with no statistical significance ($r= 0.17-0.123$). Given this discrepancy between perception and knowledge, outcome measurement for an EBP Fellowship program should therefore combine both subjective and objective outcomes (Wonder et al., 2017).

Conclusion

The positive impact of utilizing EBP is demonstrated through improved patient outcomes, organizational safety, and nurse job satisfaction. Researchers have identified a number of barriers to nurse engagement in EBP, the most significant being lack of the knowledge and the skills needed to complete the steps of EBP. Not surprisingly, the most frequently reported facilitator to EBP utilization was identified as education. Among the methods of education noted in the literature, one of the most effective is a long-term education program in the form of an EBP Fellowship Program. Evidence demonstrates that a one-year program comprised of monthly didactic classes and dedicated EBP work time is effective in improving nurses' EBP knowledge and implementation. When planning an EBP Fellowship Program, identification of outcome measures is crucial to determine program effectiveness. A combination of both objective and subjective measures will help to validate program success through both knowledge transfer and change in perception and self-confidence.

METHODS

Several steps were taken to fulfill this project's purpose of developing a one-year EBP Fellowship Program. Due to the complexity and length of the program as well as a current lack of funding, the program will not be fully implemented as part of this DNP project; however, the project resulted in the development of all aspects of the program for future implementation.

Setting

The EBP Fellowship Program was developed for implementation at CHLA's main hospital facility with input and oversight from nurse administrators and nurse researchers. A number of PhD and DNP-prepared nurses with relevant expertise are currently employed by CHLA and will serve as subject-matter experts and mentors for the program. The JHNEBP Model will serve as the framework for the program curriculum, as it is utilized for EBP activities throughout the organization.

Sample

Program participants will be nurses who have at least 18 months' experience in either the inpatient or outpatient setting at CHLA. An initial cohort of eight nurses will be selected through an application process. As part of the application, nurses will be asked to submit a short written essay about the topic that they wish to evaluate as part of an EBP project. All applicants will be expected to submit a letter of support from their direct supervisor to be considered for the program. A subcommittee of the Clinical Services Research Council will review and score applications and make decisions regarding acceptance into the program.

Ethical Issues

Approval by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of both CHLA and California State University, Los Angeles was obtained prior to the program's development. Because no human subjects were utilized in the development of the program, an IRB waiver was obtained, thus classifying the project as non-research activity. Prior to full program implementation in the future, additional IRB approval will be requested through CHLA to ensure protection of program participants. Because participants will be asked to complete two measures for program evaluation prior to and after completion of the program, steps will be taken to ensure that results are anonymous and reported only as aggregate data.

Program Development and Timeline

Methods for this project included the development of the program curriculum, budget, application, application scoring rubric, participant guidelines, and class schedule. Each of these components was completed as of January 2019. Additionally, a budget proposal was submitted to hospital administrators in January 2019. All components were developed based on evidence and input from PhD and DNP-prepared nurses at CHLA. These nurses are expert in the generation and appraisal of evidence, as well as the culture and operational practices of the organization, and provided valuable insight into the program's curriculum. PhD nurses were utilized to develop and review curriculum related to evidence appraisal, while DNP nurses were utilized to drive content related to research translation. The curriculum is based on the steps in the JHNEBP PET Process.

Evaluation Methods

The program's success will be evaluated by the achievement of three outcomes: transfer of knowledge, increase in nurses' EBP confidence, and implementation of EBP. Transfer of knowledge will be measured using the EKAN (see Table 5), a valid and reliable tool which objectively measures a nurse's knowledge related to EBP. The EKAN will be administered prior to the first curriculum component and after completion of the program. Mean and median scores will be compared to determine whether an increase in knowledge has occurred through program participation. Permission to use the EKAN tool can be found in Appendix C. The EKAN tool can be found in Appendix D.

Nurses' confidence in EBP will be measured using the EBPSE scale (see Table 5), a valid and reliable tool which focuses on the nurse's perception of their ability to perform the steps of EBP. This scale will also be administered prior to the first curriculum component and after program completion. Mean and median scores will be compared to identify whether a change in self-efficacy has occurred throughout the program. Permission to use the EBPSE scale is located in Appendix E. The EBPSE scale can be found in Appendix F.

Measurement of EBP implementation will be based on the number of projects completed annually at CHLA, tied to when the EBP Fellowship Program is officially started. The CHLA Clinical Services Research and EBP Database will be monitored to determine the number of projects completed annually by nurses who did not participate in the RN Residency program. A percentage increase in the number of projects completed annually will be calculated and reported as a part of the program's outcomes.

RESULTS

All of the EBP Fellowship Program components were developed using evidence gathered through a review of literature, as well as input gathered from experts at CHLA. The curriculum is comprised of monthly classes with a focus on leveraging the JHNEBP Model to guide participants through the process of conducting an EBP project from question development, and culminating with translation and dissemination. The curriculum is designed to facilitate the development of skill through experiential learning, with fellows participating in a class and then immediately applying the knowledge they have gained to their individual project.

Curriculum

Curricular components for the EBP Fellowship Program include development of an EBP question, searching for evidence, quantitative and qualitative research methodology, basic statistical interpretation, critical appraisal of evidence, action planning, and dissemination. The full curriculum schedule can be found in Appendix G, with curriculum outcomes located in Appendix H. One of the challenges in designing this program was identifying how to ensure that interventions moved into translation are truly evidence-based and appropriate for practice at CHLA, while also ensuring that all fellows are able to successfully complete the program. It is not uncommon, especially within pediatrics, to synthesize evidence only to find that an insufficient amount of evidence supports a change. Recommendations after the evidence appraisal phase of EBP may include translation of an intervention into practice, continuation of current practice, continuation of current practice with quality improvement needed to ensure that

processes are optimized, and research to generate knowledge about a topic with insufficient evidence.

Unique to this fellowship program are the tracks available for each fellow after the fifth month of class. Following evidence synthesis and recommendation development, fellows will collaborate with the program facilitator to determine which track is most appropriate for their project. Nurse researchers within the Institute for Nursing and Interprofessional Research (INIR) at CHLA are prepared and willing to support the design of a pilot study for those who wish to pursue research. Experts from the Quality Department at CHLA are prepared to support quality improvement work that stems from the fellowship program. Change experts will be available to support fellows who aim to move their EBP projects into intervention translation.

Lastly, for those fellows who do not have sufficient evidence to support translation but who do not wish to pursue research, a fourth track entitled the “Scholars” track, will allow the fellow to collaborate with the program facilitator to identify another EBP topic or topics, with a focus on appraisal of evidence to add to CHLA’s body of research knowledge. Provision of several contingent opportunities for fellows will help to ensure that each fellow is able to participate for the entire year without feeling compelled to translate a poorly-supported intervention into practice.

Program Components

A set of program guidelines (Appendix I) was developed to ensure that all applicants and participants know the expectations prior to committing to the program. An application (Appendix J) and application scoring rubric (Appendix K) were developed to ensure fair consideration of each applicant. During the course of the fellowship,

participants will be held accountable to ensure that they are making use of their time appropriately and to ensure that any issues or challenges are identified and mitigated as quickly as possible. For this reason, a Project Progress Report (Appendix L) was developed. This tool will be completed by fellows on a monthly basis and turned in to the program facilitator two weeks prior to each class day. This will allow the facilitator to review for any issues, identify potential solutions, and meet with the fellow individually during the class day to strategize as needed to ensure that fellows are able to meet deadlines and follow their established timeline for project completion.

IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

Timeline

The EBP Fellowship Program is anticipated to launch in July 2019 with a pilot cohort of eight fellows. Emails and announcements about the fellowship program will be released in March 2019, with applications opening in April. Final participant selection will be completed no later than June 1, 2019. Participants will be expected to review the program guidelines (see Appendix I) and confirm their commitment to the program for the full year prior to acceptance. The program guidelines specify the expectations for each fellow provide answers to a number of anticipated questions related to the program.

Budget

A program budget was created to justify the cost of the program. Because the facilitator and subject-matter experts are all exempt staff members who are paid a salary, rather than an hourly rate, the majority of cost for the program will be the hourly pay for participants. Given an average hourly rate of \$40 per hour, and the fact that the program will allot a total of 12 hours each month for one year to the fellows for participation in a six-hour class with an additional six hours for independent work time, the projected total salary budget for eight fellows is \$46,080. Additional expenses are minimal, as rooms and audiovisual equipment will be supplied free of charge by CHLA. The only remaining cost associated with the program will be the printing of posters for dissemination. As the average cost of poster printing is \$80 using CHLA's preferred vendor, a total cost for this is estimated to be \$640. This brings the entire budget for the program to \$46,720. This budget has been presented to research and administrative

leaders at CHLA, and at this time partial funding has been secured through the INIR and the remaining funding is being sought through a private donor.

ANTICIPATED RESULTS

Participation

Given the enthusiasm and interest demonstrated by CHLA nurses for other EBP course offerings, it is expected that this new program will be well-received and receive a large number of applicants. The fellowship program provides an opportunity to overcome barriers to EBP related to lack of knowledge and lack of time, two of the most prevalent issues facing CHLA nurses. PhD and DNP-prepared nurses at CHLA have already demonstrated interest in the program through their willingness to collaborate in planning the program; many have expressed interest in serving as subject-matter experts and mentors for program participants.

Outcomes

Outcome measures for this program will include a change over time in participant EBP knowledge and confidence, as well as the number of completed EBP projects each year. It is expected that implementation of this program will result in the completion of a higher number of EBP projects in the coming years as compared to previous years, given the program's ability to support this work. Higher participant EKAN and EBPSE scores are expected following completion of the program, thus demonstrating that through participation, fellows will have gained a higher level of EBP knowledge and will have increased their confidence in conducting EBP inquiries. Demonstration of these outcomes will help to justify the expenditures needed to grow the program in subsequent years, allowing for more nurses to participate in a larger cohort.

Challenges

Anticipated challenges for the program include advocating for and maintaining funding levels, ensuring adequate staffing coverage to allow for participation, ensuring consistency between mentors, and the potential for additional funding being needed to support project translation, such as for new equipment or supplies. Funding will be addressed by demonstrating positive program outcomes and creating a strong justification to support the need for the program at CHLA. The requirement for manager statement of support as part of the application should help to mitigate issues regarding staffing, ensuring that managers are aware of committed to supporting the fellow's participation in the program. A short meeting will be held for mentors to go over the program components and establish clear expectations, and the program facilitator will serve as a support for mentors to establish as much consistency as possible. The INIR offers EBP grants of up to \$2500 to support project translation; grant application support will be offered for fellows wishing to obtain additional funds to support equipment and supply needs for translation.

DISCUSSION

CHLA currently has a strong existing infrastructure to support research and quality improvement, but a distinct lack of support for EBP. Given that the evidence clearly demonstrates the need for research utilization in practice and establishes that barriers to EBP engagement include lack of time, knowledge and skill, and resources, it is imperative that leaders at CHLA identify opportunities to overcome these barriers and support nurses in this increasingly important work. The implementation of an EBP Fellowship will help to develop a culture of inquiry within the organization, providing protected time, instruction, support, and access to all the resources necessary for success. Providing nurses with the opportunity to grow their knowledge and skill in translating evidence into practice will likely result in improved patient care and will ultimately result in cost savings through improved patient outcomes. The positive effects of EBP engagement go beyond patient care. As demonstrated by the evidence, this program has the potential to improve nurse satisfaction, group cohesion, and sense of autonomy in practice. This in turn can help to increase retention rates and reduce costs related to nurse turnover.

As the business and science of health care rapidly advances, so must the practice of nursing. Nurse engagement in EBP helps to ensure that patients receive care based on the most reliable and current evidence; this is vital to improving the health and welfare of individuals, communities, and society as a whole. Health care organizations must leverage creative strategies to eliminate barriers and promote a culture of inquiry and EBP within the nursing workforce, thus moving their agencies and the nursing profession forward in their continuous pursuit of promoting best practices for the patients we serve.

REFERENCES

- Balakas, K., Sparks, L., Steurer, L., & Bryant, T. (2013). An outcome of evidence-based practice education: Sustained clinical decision-making among bedside nurses. *Journal of Pediatric Nursing, 28*(5), 479-485. doi:10.1016/j.pedn.2012.08.007
- Balas, E. A., & Boren, S. A. (2000). Managing clinical knowledge for health care improvement. *Yearbook of Medical Information*(1), 65-70.
- Barnsteiner, J. H., Reeder, V. C., Palma, W. H., Preston, A. M., & Walton, M. K. (2010). Promoting evidence-based practice and translational research. *Nursing Administration Quarterly, 34*(3), 217-225. doi:10.1097/NAQ.0b013e3181e702f4
- Bartlett, J. A., & Allen, N. H. (2013). Increasing organizational evidence based practice capacity through an evidence based practice scholars program. *Journal of Pediatric Nursing, 28*(4), 413-414. doi:10.1016/j.pedn.2013.04.003
- Bissett, K., Cvach, M., & White, K. (2016). Improving competence and confidence with evidence-based practice among nurses: Outcomes of a quality improvement project. *Journal for Nurses in Professional Development, 32*(5), 248-255. doi:10.1097/NND.0000000000000293
- Brown, C. E., Ecoff, L., Kim, S. C., Wickline, M. A., Rose, B., Klimpel, K., & Glaser, D. (2010). Multi-institutional study of barriers to research utilisation and evidence-based practice among hospital nurses. *Journal of Clinical Nursing, 19*(13/14), 1944-1951. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2702.2009.03184.x

- Brown, C. E., Wickline, M. A., Ecoff, L., & Glaser, D. (2009). Nursing practice, knowledge, attitudes and perceived barriers to evidence-based practice at an academic medical center. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 65(2), 371-381.
doi:10.1111/j.1365-2648.2008.04878.x
- Cadmus, E., Van Wynen, E., Chamberlain, B., Steingall, P., Kilgallen, M. E., Holly, C., & Gallagher-Ford, L. (2008). Nurses' skill level and access to evidence-based practice. *JONA: The Journal of Nursing Administration*, 38(11), 494-503.
doi:10.1097/01.NNA.0000339471.42596.18
- Chang, A. M., & Crowe, L. (2011). Validation of scales measuring self-efficacy and outcome expectancy in evidence-based practice. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 8(2), 106. doi:10.1111/j.1741-6787.2011.00215.x
- Children's Hospital Los Angeles. (2018). Clinical services research and evidence-based practice database. In.
- Christenbery, T., Williamson, A., Sandlin, V., & Wells, N. (2016). Immersion in evidence-based practice fellowship program: A transforming experience for staff nurses. *Journal for Nurses in Professional Development*, 32(1), 15-20.
doi:10.1097/nnd.0000000000000197
- Chummun, H., & Tiran, D. (2008). Increasing research evidence in practice: a possible role for the consultant nurse. *Journal of Nursing Management*, 16(3), 327-333.
doi:10.1111/j.1365-2834.2007.00791.x
- Dang, D., & Dearholt, S. (2017). *Johns Hopkins nursing evidence-based practice: Model and guidelines* (3rd ed. ed.). Indianapolis, IN: Indianapolis, IN : Sigma Theta Tau International.

- Eizenberg, M. M. (2011). Implementation of evidence-based nursing practice: Nurses' personal and professional factors. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 67(1), 33. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2648.2010.05488.x
- Gale, B. V., & Schaffer, A. M. (2009). Organizational readiness for evidence-based practice. *JONA: The Journal of Nursing Administration*, 39(2), 91-97. doi:10.1097/NNA.0b013e318195a48d
- Gattuso, J. S., Hinds, P. S., Beaumont, C., Funk, A. J., Green, J., Max, A., . . . Windsor, K. (2007). Transforming a hospital nursing research fellowship into an evidence-based practice fellowship. *JONA: The Journal of Nursing Administration*, 37(12), 539-545.
- Gawlinski, A., & Becker, E. (2012). Infusing research into practice: A staff nurse evidence-based practice fellowship program. *Journal for Nurses in Professional Development*, 28(2), 69-73. doi:10.1097/NND.0b013e31824b418c
- Heater, S. B., Becker, M. A., & Olson, K. R. (1988). Nursing interventions and patient outcomes: A meta-analysis of studies. *Nursing Research*, 37(5), 303-307. doi:10.1097/00006199-198809000-00008
- Hines, S., Ramsbotham, J., & Coyer, F. (2015). The effectiveness of interventions for improving the research literacy of nurses: A systematic review. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 12(5), 265-272. doi:10.1111/wvn.12106
- Hockenberry, M., Brown, T., Walden, M., & Barrera, P. (2009). Teaching evidence-based practice skills in a hospital. *Journal of Continuing Education in Nursing*, 40(1), 28-32. doi:10.3928/00220124-20090101-08

- Institute of Medicine. (2003). *Crossing the quality chasm*. Washington, D.C.: Washington, D.C. : National Academy Press.
- Kim, S. C., Ecoff, L., Brown, C. E., Gallo, A. M., Stichler, J. F., & Davidson, J. E. (2017). Benefits of a regional evidence-based practice fellowship program: A test of the ARCC Model. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing, 14*(2), 90-98. doi:10.1111/wvn.12199
- Kim, S. C., Stichler, F. J., Ecoff, E. L., Gallo, E. A.-M., & Davidson, E. J. (2017). Six-month follow-up of a regional evidence-based practice fellowship program. *JONA: The Journal of Nursing Administration, 47*(4), 238-243. doi:10.1097/NNA.0000000000000471
- Malik, G., McKenna, L., & Griffiths, D. (2017). Using pedagogical approaches to influence evidence-based practice integration – processes and recommendations: Findings from a grounded theory study. *Journal of Advanced Nursing, 73*(4), 883-893. doi:10.1111/jan.13175
- Melnyk, B. M. (2012). Achieving a high-reliability organization through implementation of the ARCC Model for systemwide sustainability of evidence-based practice. *Nursing Administration Quarterly, 36*(2), 127-135. doi:10.1097/NAQ.0b013e318249fb6a
- Melnyk, B. M., & Fineout-Overholt, E. (2005). *Evidence-based practice in nursing and healthcare: A guide to best practice*. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.

- Melnyk, B. M., Fineout-Overholt, E., Gallagher-Ford, L., & Kaplan, L. (2012). The state of evidence-based practice in US nurses: Critical implications for nurse leaders and educators. *JONA: The Journal of Nursing Administration*, 42(9), 410-417. doi:10.1097/NNA.0b013e3182664e0a
- Melnyk, B. M., Fineout-Overholt, E., Gigglesman, M., & Cruz, R. (2010). Correlates among cognitive beliefs, EBP implementation, organizational culture, cohesion and job satisfaction in evidence-based practice mentors from a community hospital system. *Nursing Outlook*, 58(6), 301-308. doi:10.1016/j.outlook.2010.06.002
- Melnyk, B. M., Gallagher-Ford, L., Zellefrow, C., Tucker, S., Thomas, B., Sinnott, L. T., & Tan, A. (2018). The first US study on nurses' evidence-based practice competencies indicates major deficits that threaten healthcare quality, safety, and patient outcomes. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 15(1), 16-25. doi:10.1111/wvn.12269
- Milne, D. J., Krishnasamy, M., Johnston, L., & Aranda, S. (2007). Promoting evidence-based care through a clinical research fellowship programme. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 16(9), 1629-1639. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2702.2007.01748.x
- Moore, L. (2017). Effectiveness of an online educational module in improving evidence-based practice skills of practicing registered nurses. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 14(5), 358-366. doi:10.1111/wvn.12214
- Mori, C. (2015). Implementing evidence-based practice to reduce infections following arthroplasty. *Orthopaedic Nursing*, 34(4), 188-194. doi:10.1097/NOR.0000000000000157

- Pipe, T. B., Timm, J. A., Harris, M. R., Frusti, D. K., Tucker, S., Attlesey-Pries, J. M., . . . Scherb, C. (2009). Implementing a health system-wide evidence-based practice educational program to reach nurses with various levels of experience and educational preparation. *Nursing Clinics of North America*, *44*(1), 43-55.
doi:10.1016/j.cnur.2008.10.008
- Pravikoff, D. S., Tanner, A. B., & Pierce, S. T. (2005). Readiness of U.S nurses for evidence-based practice. *American Journal of Nursing*, *105*(9), 40-51.
doi:10.1097/00000446-200509000-00025
- Prior, P., Wilkinson, J., & Neville, S. (2010). Practice nurse use of evidence in clinical practice: a descriptive survey. *Nursing Praxis in New Zealand*, *26*(2), 14.
- Saunders, H., Stevens, K., & Vehvilainen-Julkunen, K. (2016). Nurses' readiness for evidence-based practice at Finnish university hospitals: A national survey. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, *72*(8), 1863-1874. doi:10.1111/jan.12963
- Selig, M. P., & Lewanowicz, M. W. (2008). Translation to practice: Developing an evidence-based practice nurse internship program. *AACN Advanced Critical Care*, *19*(3), 325-332. doi:10.1097/01.AACN.0000330384.64637.14
- Steurer, L. M. (2010). An evidence-based practice scholars program: one institution's journey toward excellence. *Journal of Continuing Education in Nursing*, *41*(3), 139. doi:10.3928/00220124-20100224-04
- Taylor, S., & Hall, S. (2017). Measuring success: Goals and outcomes for educational programs. *Journal of Continuing Education in Nursing*, *48*(12), 537-538.
doi:10.3928/00220124-20171115-02

- Tucker, S., Olson, M. E., & Frusti, D. K. (2009). Validity and reliability of the Evidence-Based Practice Self-Efficacy Scale. *Western Journal of Nursing Research, 31*(8), 1090-1091. doi:10.1177/0193945909342552
- Wang, C., Mark, D., Braginsky, N., & Katz, A. (2017). Offering community-based wound care as part of a comprehensive syringe exchange program. In D. Mark, N. Braginsky, & A. Katz (Eds.): ProQuest Dissertations Publishing.
- Weeks, S. M., Moore, P., & Allender, M. (2011). A regional evidence-based practice fellowship collaborating competitors. *JONA: The Journal of Nursing Administration, 41*(1), 10-14. doi:10.1097/NNA.0b013e318200282c
- Wells, N., Free, M., & Adams, R. (2007). Nursing research internship: Enhancing evidence-based practice among staff nurses. *JONA: The Journal of Nursing Administration, 37*(3), 135-143. doi:10.1097/01.NNA.0000262732.14123.a2
- Wonder, A. H., McNelis, A. M., Spurlock, D., Ironside, P. M., Lancaster, S., Davis, C. R., . . . Verwers, N. (2017). Comparison of nurses' self-reported and objectively measured evidence-based practice knowledge. *Journal of Continuing Education in Nursing, 48*(2), 65. doi:10.3928/00220124-20170119-06
- Wood, E. B., Harrison, G., Trickey, A., Friesen, M. A., Stinson, S., Rovelli, E., . . . Presgrave, K. (2017). Evidence-based practice: Video-discharge instructions in the pediatric emergency department. *Journal of Emergency Nursing, 43*(4), 316-321. doi:10.1016/j.jen.2016.11.003
- Yoder, L. H., Kirkley, D., McFall, D. C., Kirksey, K. M., Stalbaum, A. L., & Sellers, D. (2014). Staff nurses' use of research to facilitate evidence-based practice. *American Journal of Nursing, 114*(9), 26-37.

APPENDIX A

PERMISSION TO USE THE JOHNS HOPKINS NURSING EVIDENCE-BASED PRACTICE MODEL

HERE ARE YOUR JHNEBP TOOLS (AND A SURPRISE GIFT)!

Thank you for your submission. We are happy to give you permission to use the JHEBP model and tool in adherence of our legal terms mentioned noted below:

- You may not modify the model or the tools without written approval from Johns Hopkins.
- All reference to source forms should include "©The Johns Hopkins Hospital/The Johns Hopkins University."
- The tools may not be used for commercial purposes without special permission.
- If interested in commercial use or discussing changes to the tool, please email ijhn@jhmi.edu.

Click [HERE](#) to access the 2013 zipped file of the tools. These tools correspond to the 2nd edition of the book.
Click [HERE](#) to access the 2017 zipped file of the tools. These tools correspond to the 3rd edition of the book.

You can learn more about the 2017 updated model and tools [HERE](#).

Please note: If you choose to use the Johns Hopkins Nursing Evidence-Based Practice Model and Tools in any other way, another form will need to be submitted.

APPENDIX B
TABLES OF EVIDENCE

Table 1

Significance and Benefits of EBP.

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
To assess the state of research translation in health care (Balas & Boren, 2000)	Literature review	No sample	Comparison of landmark trials with current usage rate of specific clinical procedures	Average of 17 years between publication of landmark trial and at least 50% use rate in clinical practice	Provides evidence of disconnect between knowledge generation and knowledge translation Dated but classic; no new estimates exist suggesting that this lag has improved
To determine the extent to which EBP leads to improved patient outcomes (Heater et al., 1988)	Systematic review with meta-analysis; focus on behavioral, knowledge, psychological, and psychosocial outcomes IV = nursing interventions DV = patient outcomes	84 studies with more than 4,000 subjects ranging from preterm infant to elderly	d-index for determining effect size	Mean ES for all outcomes is .59 with U3= 72.2	Evidence-based nursing interventions led to a 28% improvement in patient outcomes over procedural nursing care. Study is dated but classic Demonstrates importance of EBP in improving patient outcomes
To discuss the similarities and intersections	Literature review and expert opinion	No sample	Comparison of HRHOs with EBP culture	EBP closely aligns with HRHOs	Use of EBP can contribute to increased safety and decreased variation in care leading to improved patient outcomes;

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
between EBP and HRHOs (Melnyk, 2012)					EBP can position HCOs to become HRHOs
To determine the effects of EBP education on nurses' sense of group cohesion and job satisfaction (Melnyk et al., 2010)	Descriptive correlational study IV = participation in EBP mentorship program DV = EBP implementation, group cohesion, job satisfaction	58 nurses and health care professionals participating in an EBP mentorship program	OCRSIEP scale, EBPB scale, EBPI scale, Group Cohesion Scale, Price & Mueller Job Satisfaction questionnaire	Positive correlation between EBP beliefs and job satisfaction ($p < 0.05$), group cohesion ($p < 0.01$), and EBP implementation ($p < 0.01$)	Relationship exists between EBP beliefs and group cohesion and job satisfaction Small sample size, limited to one hospital

Note. EBP = evidence-based practice; EBPB = Evidence-based Practice Beliefs; EBPI = Evidence-based Practice Implementation; ES = effect size; HCO = health care organization; HRHO = high reliability health care organization; OCRSIEP = Organizational Culture and Readiness for System-wide Integration of Evidence-based Practice

Table 2

Barriers and Facilitators for EBP Utilization Among Nurses

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
To study relationship between perceived barriers to EBP and actual implementation of EBP (Brown et al., 2010)	Cross-sectional survey study IV = perceived barriers to EBP implementation DV = implementation of EBP	1301 nurses from 4 Southern California hospital systems	BARRIERS scale (including adopter, organization, innovation and communication subscales) and EBQP	<p>Adopter subscale showed negative correlation with EBP attitudes and knowledge/skills ($p \leq 0.01$) but no correlation to practice of EBP.</p> <p>Organization subscale showed negative correlation with EBP attitudes ($p \leq 0.05$) and knowledge/skills ($p \leq 0.01$) but not to practice of EBP.</p> <p>Innovation subscale showed negative correlation with EBP attitudes ($p \leq 0.05$) but not with knowledge/skills or EBP practice.</p> <p>Communication subscale showed negative correlation with EBP attitudes, knowledge/skill and EBP practice ($p \leq 0.01$).</p>	<p>Barriers to EBP exist but may not be predictive of EBP utilization.</p> <p>Most frequently reported barriers included lack of time to read research, insufficient time to implement change, and lack of knowledge about research.</p> <p>Limitations include convenience sample and inability to derive cause and effect from survey.</p>

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
To identify barriers and facilitators for EBP implementation (Brown et al., 2009)	Descriptive, cross-sectional survey	Convenience, non-probability sample 458 nurses from one academic medical center in Southern California	BARRIERS and EBPQ	Most significant barriers included lack of time to implement (mean = 2.94/5), lack of time to read research (mean = 2.91/5), lack of research knowledge (mean = 2.73/5), and lack of authority (mean = 2.70/5)	Major barriers to EBP implementation include lack of time, knowledge, and perceived authority Limited sample and location
To identify barriers to nurse engagement in EBP and to determine whether Magnet and non-Magnet hospitals have differences in nurse EBP skill level and access to EBP resources (Cadmus et al., 2008)	Descriptive survey (quantitative) with qualitative response section IV = Magnet designation DV = EBP skill and resource access	3411 acute care nurses representing 32 hospitals in New Jersey	ILEBNP instrument	Top individual barriers identified include lack of skills to critique research, lack of knowledge for searching literature, and lack of access to research. Top institutional barriers include lack of budget for EBP training, conflicting organizational goals, and lack of budget for resources. Magnet designation demonstrated a positive correlation to librarian access ($p < 0.01$), internet access ($p < 0.01$), access to CINAHL and MEDLINE ($p < 0.01$), and research	Major barriers to EBP implementation include lack of knowledge and skill, lack of resource access, lack of organizational budget, lack of support, and lack of time. Nurses in Magnet hospitals have access to more resources and are more likely to engage in EBP. Limited sample from one state

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
				utilization and participation ($p < 0.01$). Qualitative section barriers supported quantitative data with additional barriers of lack of management support and lack of time	
To determine current state of EBP utilization by nurses and barriers to using EBP in nursing practice (Chummun & Tiran, 2008)	Literature review	25 research articles from United States and Europe	N/A	Major reported barriers for EBP include lack of time, lack of knowledge/skill to appraise research, and lack of organizational support for EBP	Barriers such as time and lack of knowledge must be mitigated for widespread EBP implementation Organizations must prioritize EBP and provide necessary support to build EBP cultures
To determine correlation between personal and professional factors and nurses' use of EBP (Eizenberg, 2011)	Cross-sectional survey IV = personal and professional factors (computer/internet access, resource access, role DV = EBP utilization	243 hospital and community nurses in northern Israel	Demographics, EBP attitudes scale, EBP barriers and support scale, and EBP behavior scale	Nurses in managerial roles ($p = 0.01$) and with higher education ($p = 0.02$) were more likely to engage in EBP Nurses with access to computers ($p = 0.03$), internet ($p = 0.01$), and library ($p = 0.04$) were more likely to engage in EBP Nurses who reported high levels of confidence in their knowledge to appraise literature were	Barriers to EBP include lack of computer and internet access, lack of education, and lack of support Facilitators include computer and internet access, library and resource support, and education Limited sample from Israel based on self-report; most recruited participants were students and other interested nurses from snowball recruitment; bias likely

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
				2.55 times more likely to engage in EBP ($p < 0.01$) and nurses who reported having support for finding and appraising research were 1.48 times more likely to engage in EBP ($p = 0.02$)	
To determine factors affecting EBP implementation among nurses (Gale & Schaffer, 2009)	Descriptive survey	67 clinical nurses and 20 nurse managers from one acute care hospital	EBPC Survey, developed by researcher and validated by content experts. No reliability testing conducted.	Most reported barriers were lack of time, lack of staff, and lack of resources Nurses with less than 3 years' experience cited lack of time more frequently than experienced nurses ($p = 0.38$)	Barriers to EBP implementation include lack of time, insufficient staffing, and inadequate access to resources Barriers must be mitigated for successful development of EBP culture Limited to small sample size in one hospital; survey reliability not established
To determine nurses' perceptions of EBP, nurses' needs for EBP implementation, and whether education level and Magnet designation creates differences in EBP perceptions and needs among nurses (Melnik et al., 2012)	Descriptive survey IV = nurse education level and Magnet status DV = EBP perceptions and needs	1015 nurses from across the US	Researcher-developed survey with demographic questions and 18 questions about EBP; reliability and validity established prior to survey administration	32.5% reported access to EBP mentors in their organization 76.2% reported the need to learn more about EBP 61.5% reported interest in online EBP training 75.3% reported need for tools to implement EBP	Nurses need access to EBP education, EBP mentorship, and tools for success in implementing EBP Limited by low response rate (5%) and sample derived only from ANA members

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
				<p>69% reported interest in EBP fellowship program with expert mentors</p> <p>Nurses in Magnet hospitals reported higher levels of EBP implementation, ($p < 0.001$), access to EBP mentors ($p < 0.001$), access to EBP education ($p < 0.001$), and an organizational culture that support EBP ($p < 0.001$)</p> <p>Nurses without master's degrees reported more need for EBP education ($p < 0.001$) and higher interest in educational offerings ($p < 0.001$)</p> <p>Nurses with master's degrees reported higher confidence with EBP ($p < 0.001$)</p>	
To determine current level of EBP competency among nurses and to identify factors that affect EBP competency	Cross-sectional descriptive survey	2,344 nurses from 19 hospitals across the US	Demographics, EBP knowledge scale, EBPB scale, EBPI scale, OCSIEP scale, EBP mentorship	<p>Average EBP competency score is 53.5/96.</p> <p>Younger nurses and more highly educated nurses</p>	<p>More EBP education and mentorship is needed to increase EBP competency for US nurses</p> <p>Limited by convenience sample, only 19 hospitals represented</p>

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
(Melnik et al., 2018)			scale, and EBP competency scale.	had higher EBP competency ($p < 0.001$)	
			Knowledge, mentorship, and competency scales developed by researchers for this study; reliability and validity established prior to survey administration	Nurses with access to EBP mentoring had a greater likelihood of implementing EBP ($p < 0.001$)	
To examine nurses' EBP skill perception and access to EBP resources and tools (Pravikoff et al., 2005)	Descriptive, exploratory survey	760 clinical nurses from across the US with geographic stratification	93-item survey Content validity established; no mention of reliability testing	58% of respondents reported not using research to support practice 57% reported no access to medical library 36% reported having access to electronic databases through work 76% reported having never searched CINAHL 58% reported never having searched MEDLINE	Barriers to EBP include lack of access to databases and knowledge about finding and utilizing research Authors conclude that US nurses require more EBP education to successfully and consistently implement EBP Limited by low response rate (37%) Survey did not assess time or mentorship as barriers to EBP Survey reliability unknown

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
				Top reported barriers to EBP implementation include lack of value for research, lack of knowledge in searching electronic databases, and inability to access research	
To assess nurses' perceptions of EBP utilization, attitudes, and knowledge/skill (Prior et al., 2010)	Descriptive survey IV = EBP knowledge/skill, EBP attitudes, length of time as nurse DV = EBP implementation	55 nurses in West Auckland, New Zealand	EBPQ	Knowledge and skill had a positive correlation to EBP implementation ($p < 0.001$) EBP attitudes had a positive correlation with EBP implementation ($p < 0.001$) Length of time as a nurse had a negative correlation with time spent reading professional journals ($p < 0.038$)	Increasing EBP knowledge and skill are key to improving nurse implementation of EBP Negative attitudes toward EBP must be overcome to improve EBP implementation Limited by small sample size in one part of New Zealand and low response rate (50%)
To assess readiness for EBP among nurses in Finnish hospitals and to determine the relationship between EBP self-efficacy and EBP knowledge	Descriptive cross-sectional survey Comparison of EBP confidence with EBP knowledge	943 RNs in urban university hospital systems in Finland	Stevens' EBP Readiness Inventory-measures both self-efficacy and perceived knowledge about EBP	RNs who rated themselves at an intermediate or advanced level of EBP knowledge have significantly higher levels of confidence in EBP implementation	Authors conclude that Finnish nurses are not ready for EBP use in practice; self-efficacy and confidence needs to be built through education to increase knowledge Limitations include 50% response rate to survey; results may be

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
(Saunders et al., 2016)					skewed due to characteristics which would make an RN more likely to respond Study underpins the need to provide EBP education to increase nurses' confidence and ultimate readiness to employ EBP in practice
To assess personal and organizational factors that affect EBP implementation among nurses (Yoder et al., 2014)	Cross-sectional descriptive survey	1112 nurses from 10 hospitals in south central Texas	53-item survey adapted from Research Utilization in Nursing survey; reliability and validity of adapted study established prior to survey administration	75% of respondents reported use of personal experience in clinical decision-making 23% reported using research in clinical decision-making 7% reported participation in journal clubs 16% reported use of a medical library 45% reported use of CINAHL or MEDLINE 7% reported access to support for literature searches	Organizational culture must support EBP as primary method of clinical decision-making Resources such as journal clubs, librarians, and databases are needed to ensure access to research Limited by small sample size in one health system

Note. ANA = American Nurses Association; EBP = evidence-based practice; EBPB = Evidence-Based Practice Beliefs; EBPC = Evidence-Based Practice Changes; EBPI = Evidence-Based Practice Implementation; EBPQ = Evidence-Based Practice Questionnaire; ILEBNP = Information Literacy for Evidence-Based Nursing Practice; OCRSIEP = Organizational Culture and Readiness for System-wide Integration of Evidence-based Practice

Table 3

Methods of EBP Education.

Purpose	Deisgn/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
To determine efficacy of nurse EBP Scholars program in developing regular use of EBP for clinical decision-making, and specifically to determine the factors that affect nurses' use of EBP for clinical decision-making (Balakas et al., 2013)	Qualitative-interpretive phenomenological study	No sample	Comparison of landmark trials with current usage rate of specific clinical procedures	Average of 17 years between publication of landmark trial and at least 50% use rate in clinical practice	Provides evidence of disconnect between knowledge generation and knowledge translation Dated but classic; no new estimates exist suggesting that this lag has improved
To describe systems and resources necessary for EBP adoption by clinical nurses (Barnsteiner et al., 2010)	Program report; no research design	84 studies with more than 4,000 subjects ranging from preterm infant to elderly	d-index for determining effect size	Mean ES for all outcomes is .59 with U3= 72.2	Evidence-based nursing interventions led to a 28% improvement in patient outcomes over procedural nursing care. Study is dated but classic Demonstrates importance of EBP in improving patient outcomes
To evaluate the effects of an EBP education bundle (Bissett et al., 2016)	Quality improvement project with pretest/posttest measurement	No sample	Comparison of HRHOs with EBP culture	EBP closely aligns with HRHOs	Use of EBP can contribute to increased safety and decreased variation in care leading to improved patient outcomes; EBP can position HCOs to become HRHOs

Purpose	Deisgn/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
To assess effectiveness of educational strategies and interventions on improving nurses' EBP skills (Hines et al., 2015)	Systematic review IV = EBP education DV = EBP knowledge/skills, EBP implementation, EBP self-efficacy	58 nurses and health care professionals participating in an EBP mentorship program	OCRSIEP scale, EBPB scale, EBPI scale, Group Cohesion Scale, Price & Mueller Job Satisfaction questionnaire	Positive correlation between EBP beliefs and job satisfaction ($p < 0.05$), group cohesion ($p < 0.01$), and EBP implementation ($p < 0.01$)	Relationship exists between EBP beliefs and group cohesion and job satisfaction Small sample size, limited to one hospital
To identify methods used by instructors to teach EBP in nursing (Malik et al., 2017)	Qualitative-Grounded theory study	23 academic staff members from Australian universities	Semi-structured interviews and observation; data analysis timed concurrently with data collection until saturation achieved	Participants reported that using a variety of teaching strategies was most effective, and that active involvement with learners doing the work of EBP, as opposed to passive learning, results in more engaged students	Acquisition of knowledge and skill through developing individual skills in critical appraisal is not as effective as learner engagement in EBP process, which is vital to effective teaching Sample may be skewed due to voluntary participation Supports use of active engagement of learners in EBP; classes teaching concepts is insufficient for effective knowledge transfer
To establish efficacy of an online EBP educational module (Moore, 2017)	Quasi-experimental pretest/posttest IV = EBP educational module, alternate education module, or no education module DV = EBP knowledge, skill, and attitude	77 nurses working in a large regional hospital	EBPQ	No statistically significant difference in outcomes between the 3 groups	Online module may not be effective for EBP education Authors suggest that multiple educational interventions are needed to build EBP culture Instrument only collected subjective data about participants' perceptions; no objective data reflecting actual knowledge or skill was collected

Note. EBP = evidence-based practice; EKAN = Evidence-Based Practice Knowledge Assessment in Nursing; EBPQ = Evidence-Based Practice Questionnaire; EBPSE = Evidence-Based Practice Self-Efficacy

Table 4

Summary of Studies Including High-Fidelity Simulation in Hospital Staff Education

Program	Program Characteristics	Participants	Outcomes	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
EBP Scholars Program (Bartlett & Allen, 2013)	Interprofessional program Acceptance based on application and interviews 6-week weekly didactic program then 7 hours per month Participants can continue in program if able to meet 7 hours/month expectation	Total of 42 participants since program implementation, 16 continuing for more than 1 year	Literature appraisal- 421 pieces of evidence analyzed Tenure- 16 Scholars continued into second year of program Advanced Degrees- 8 Scholars have progressed to seeking advanced degrees after program participation Magnet Exemplars- Scholars program has resulted in 2 SOE exemplars for Magnet status	Flexible program length, no specific goal of completing EBP project with implementation Small number of total participants Opportunity for more rigorous outcome measurement
EBP Fellowship Program (Christenbery et al., 2016)	One year program Fellows focus on one topic of interest and follow through full EBP process 8 hours/month guaranteed time away from clinical work Poster presentations after program at Nursing Research Day	22-35 nurses per year with 50-74% completion rate	Focus group conducted Emerging themes from focus groups included support, resources, empowerment, gained knowledge, and opportunity	Participation in year-long EBP program with specific project provides increase in knowledge, sense of empowerment, and access to support needed for success Creation and presentation of professional posters provides additional level of professional development and experience with dissemination

Program	Program Characteristics	Participants	Outcomes	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
EBP Fellowship Program (Gattuso et al., 2007)	<p>One year program</p> <p>Eligibility criteria included minimum 18 months' employment at organization</p> <p>Application included short essay about motivation for application</p> <p>Individual projects assigned by unit directors</p> <p>Pre-scheduled meetings between fellow and unit director to ensure adequate communication about progress</p> <p>Curriculum topics included research and EBP history data management, literature searches, evidence appraisal and levels, project implementation, abstract writing, poster development, and public speaking skills</p>	6 participants completed in first year; all 6 project implementations complete	Program evaluation conducted monthly and upon conclusion; range of scores was 3.7-4.83/5	<p>One year program is sufficient for education and project implementation</p> <p>Program leaders now working to include non-nursing professions in fellowship</p> <p>Inclusion of abstract writing, poster creation, and public speaking skills helps participants to prepare for dissemination</p>
EBP Fellowship Program	One year program directed by doctorally-prepared nurse	7 nurses selected to participate in pilot	No quantitative outcomes reported; qualitative statements indicated increased knowledge,	One year program is sufficient for completion of project

Program	Program Characteristics	Participants	Outcomes	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
(Gawlinski & Becker, 2012)	<p>6-8 hours of didactic class</p> <p>Participants receive 8 hours paid class time per month plus up to 12 additional hours per month of dedicated EBP work time</p> <p>Application includes resume, clinical issue for EBP project, and letter of support from applicant's manager or director</p> <p>Nurse Research Council reviews applications and selects participants</p> <p>Curriculum includes creation of EBP question, literature search, appraisal, and synthesis, levels of evidence, measuring outcomes, and change strategies</p>		<p>professional growth, and overall satisfaction with program</p>	<p>Application scoring matrix included in article</p> <p>Lack of outcomes measured</p> <p>Curriculum does not include dissemination strategies</p>
EBP Scholars Program (Hockenberry et al., 2009)	Full program length not noted	137 nurses at a large children's hospital	<p>No specific outcomes reported; leader and learner satisfaction noted but not supported with data</p> <p>31 complete projects reported</p>	Authors note that program has led to culture change with high value placed on EBP

Program	Program Characteristics	Participants	Outcomes	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
EBP Fellowship Program	<p>8-week didactic course followed by dedicated individual work time</p> <p>Curriculum includes problem and question development, evidence search, appraisal, and synthesis, writing evidence summaries, and translation into practice</p> <p>Program culminates with project presentations</p>	175 nurse participants in San Diego area	<p>Pretest/posttest study conducted</p> <p>Improvement in EBP beliefs ($p < 0.001$), EBP implementation ($p < 0.001$), job satisfaction ($p < 0.047$), and group cohesion ($p < 0.014$)</p>	<p>Participants in EBP fellowship demonstrate enhanced EBP beliefs, utilization of EBP, job satisfaction, and group cohesion</p> <p>Limited by lack of cause and effect, lack of randomization, and convenience sample</p>
(Kim, Ecoff, et al., 2017)	<p>Regional program</p> <p>9-month program held annually</p> <p>Six full-day didactic classes</p> <p>Participants complete EBP projects with mentor assistance</p> <p>Curriculum includes problem development, PICO question development, evidence search, appraisal, and synthesis, development of practice recommendations,</p>			

Program	Program Characteristics	Participants	Outcomes	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
	implementation, and dissemination			
EBP Fellowship Program (Kim, Stichler, et al., 2017)	Same as above	Same as above	6-month follow-up study found continued improvement in EBP Beliefs ($p < 0.001$), EBP Implementation ($p = 0.013$), and Group Cohesion ($p < 0.048$) from pretest to posttest. Positive correlation identified between EBP beliefs and adoption of EBP into work setting.	EBP Fellowship program led to increase in EBP utilization in practice by participants Limitations include lack of control group and low survey response rate (37.7%) Demonstrates efficacy of EBP fellowship in changing EBP perceptions and beliefs among participants and increasing use of EBP in work areas using a “champion” system.
Clinical Research Fellowship Program (Milne et al., 2007)	12-week interprofessional program Participants released from duties half-time for full 12 weeks with funding for backfill provided by administration Combination of didactic classes and independent work Curriculum included question development, evidence search, appraisal, and synthesis,	Total of 15 participants completed program in 2 cohorts (10 nurses, 2 occupational therapists, 1 social worker, 1 physical therapist, 1 dietician)	75% of participants plan to enroll in higher education 75% have presented at conferences 62.5% have written manuscripts for publication 87.5% have continued EBP and research work in home units 62.5% have taught critical appraisal skills to others	Program resulted in EBP implementation by participants as well as professional development Keys for program success include funding for staffing backfill, executive support, and availability of EBP experts for teaching and mentorship

Program	Program Characteristics	Participants	Outcomes	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
	implementation into practice, abstract writing, manuscript writing, and presentation skills			
National Quality Forum Scholars Initiative (Pipe et al., 2009)	Broad program focused on quality outcomes with EBP component 12 online EBP modules Curriculum included goals of EBP, role of EBP in quality outcomes, search strategies, literature search, appraisal and synthesis, outcome measures, and change theory Participants joined work groups in their individual organizations to conduct EBP projects No evidence that projects were translated into practice	91 nurses from all Mayo Clinic facilities	No outcomes measured Lessons learned included need for strategic ongoing communication with participants, demonstrating application of content to current job, providing adequate time for literature appraisal and synthesis, and clearly communicated expectations	Program sustainability for future is concerning to authors Participant diversity contributed to program success Online and distance learning modalities were necessary due to program including participants from many Mayo sites across the US Report limited by lack of reportable outcomes
EBP Nurse Internship Program (Selig & Lewanowicz, 2008)	9-month program Eligibility includes staff nurse, minimum of 1 year employment, and manager/educator	Exclusive to staff nurses; number of participants not reported	No outcomes reported Lessons learned- program now split into two 9-month sessions: learning and action phases Support offered for EBP projects that lead to research studies	Authors note high level of organizational support from executives and nurse leaders is key for program success Opportunity exists for outcomes measurement

Program	Program Characteristics	Participants	Outcomes	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
	approval prior to application			
	Ongoing support from health sciences librarian; individual meetings encouraged			
	Ongoing mentorship from educators, Research Council members, and other EBP experts			
	Curriculum includes intro to EBP, creation of PICO question, evidence search, appraisal, and synthesis, levels of evidence, and championing practice change			
EBP Scholars Program (Steurer, 2010)	6-week course Participants must develop practice question and identify recommendation for practice change by end of 6 weeks Implementation expected after completion of program	19 nurses at a large children's hospital; goal is to have at least one scholar from each unit in the hospital	Qualitative responses from participants suggest a greater level of understanding about EBP process and how to appraise evidence No quantitative data reported	Authors note that mentorship is crucial to program success Lessons learned include teaching electronic searching earlier in curriculum and scheduling 1:1 time for scholar and librarian Limited by lack of measured outcomes

Program	Program Characteristics	Participants	Outcomes	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
	<p>Curriculum includes components of EBP, developing PICO question, evidence search, appraisal, and synthesis, strategies for implementing practice change, and outcome evaluation</p> <p>EBP mentor assigned to each participant</p> <p>1:2 ratio of mentors to participants</p> <p>Mentors and librarian serve as faculty</p>			
<p>EBP Fellowship Program</p> <p>(Weeks et al., 2011)</p>	<p>Regional program for more than 40 hospitals</p> <p>9-month program with 6 full-day classes</p> <p>Each fellow has at least one mentor from their home facility</p> <p>Curriculum includes all steps in the EBP process</p> <p>Hospitals pay fee (\$1200) for nurses to participate and pay</p>	<p>Nurses from over 40 hospitals in Texas</p> <p>Number of participants per cohort or total participants not reported</p>	<p>No data reported</p>	<p>Authors note improved professional development, increased collaboration, and improved patient care as a result of fellowship program</p> <p>Limited by lack of measured outcomes</p>

Program	Program Characteristics	Participants	Outcomes	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
	nurses' salaries for 4 hours of EBP work per week			
Nursing Research Internship (Wells et al., 2007)	2-year program Curriculum includes comparison of EBP to quality improvement, conducting literature searches, appraisals, and synthesis, implementation and change strategies, outcome measurement, abstract writing, and poster creation	A total of 17 nurses have completed the program; completion rates range from 25%-41%	Past interns report using evidence in practice, starting journal clubs, taking advanced courses, and enrolling in MSN programs after participation in program	Participation in program leads to enhanced professional development and higher likelihood of utilizing EBP in the clinical setting. Limited by lack of quantitative outcomes

Note. EBP = evidence-based practice; SOE = sources of evidence

Table 5

EBP Education Outcome Measurement.

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
To establish reliability and validity of the SE-EBP and OE-EBP scales. (Chang & Crowe, 2011)	Survey to establish content reliability; factor analysis to establish construct validity; expert panel to establish content validity	174 registered nurses employed in an urban hospital in Queensland, Australia; 23% of whom had previously participated in an EBP workshop.	SE-EBP, a 26-item scale measuring nurses' level of confidence about EBP OE-EBP, an 8-item scale measuring nurses' confidence that EBP utilization will lead to improvement in patient care	Reliability of both tools established ($\alpha = 0.97$). Content validity established by expert panel. Construct validity established with KMO of 0.94	Reliability and validity of SE-EBP and OE-EBP exists. Both tools are constructed based on Sackett's 5 steps of EBP; may not be useful when paired with JHNEBP Model Limited sample, no evidence of instrument stability over time
To determine correlation between subjective and objective assessments of nurses' EBP knowledge and to further validate the EKAN tool. (Wonder et al., 2017)	Cross-sectional, descriptive, correlational design Comparison between subjective assessment of EBP skills and objective assessment of EBP knowledge.	151 nurses from two Magnet hospitals within a hospital system in Midwest	EBPQ, a 24-item scale measuring perception of knowledge, skill, attitudes, and use of EBP in practice. EKAN, a 20-item test to objectively assess nurses' knowledge related to EBP.	No statistically significant correlation between subjective assessment of EBP skills and objective assessment of EBP knowledge. Higher educational level was predictive of higher score on EKAN.	Preliminary reliability and validity established through this study. Selection of appropriate tool is key when evaluating EBP knowledge and skill. The EBPQ, measures self-perception rather than actual ability to utilize EBP. EKAN objectively measures knowledge but not skill. Sample limited to well-educated nurses within one hospital system, both Magnet facilities.

Purpose	Design/Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measures	Findings	Conclusions/Limitations/Notes
					When selecting outcomes measures for EBP fellowship, use of both subjective and objective measures will ensure capture of changes in learners' knowledge, skills, and attitudes.
To establish reliability and validity of EBPSE Scale (Tucker et al., 2009)	Quasi-experimental study to establish content validity and inter-rater reliability of the EBPSE Scale	93 participants in a year-long EBP and informatics training program	EBPSE Scale, completed by participants at beginning of program, midway through program, and upon completion	Statistical significance for reliability, with Cronbach's alpha >0.94 at each time point. Content validity established through an expert panel.	Initial indication that EBPSE Scale is reliable and valid. Limited by small cohort; further study with larger cohort is needed. Scale may be useful for EBP Fellowship program evaluation

Note. EBP = evidence-based practice; EKAN = Evidence-Based Practice Knowledge Assessment in Nursing; EBPQ = Evidence-Based Practice Questionnaire; EBPSE = Evidence-Based Practice Self-Efficacy; JHNEBP = John Hopkins Nursing Evidence-Based Practice; OE-EBP = Outcome Expectancy for EBP; SE-EBP = Self-Efficacy in EBP

APPENDIX C

EKAN TOOL SIGNED TERMS OF USE

EKAN Terms of Use

Thank you for your interest in using the Evidence-based practice Knowledge Assessment in Nursing (EKAN) instrument. You may use the EKAN, a copyrighted product by Darrell R. Spurlock Jr. PhD, RN, NEA-BC, ANEF and Amy H. Wonder, PhD, RN after agreeing to the following conditions:

- The EKAN may be used for non-commercial educational or research purposes only.
- The EKAN may not be modified without prior permission from one of the EKAN authors. Unacceptable modifications include:
 - Changing the written instructions atop the form
 - Changing the order of the items
 - Changing the numbering of the items
 - Changing the order of the item answer options (*distractors*)
 - Changing the *wording* of any item or item answer option
- Examinees may not be charged to take the EKAN.
- If the EKAN is to be administered electronically, the following conditions are met:
 - The EKAN was designed as an objective knowledge measure. To maintain security over the items and to support continued validity, **the EKAN may not be distributed electronically for examinees to take outside a secure, face-to-face testing environment. This restriction includes the remote use of “secure testing browsers” at this time.**
 - The EKAN form is re-created on the screen as it appears on paper. Page breaks in the online form should reflect those in the paper form.
 - Once examinees have submitted/completed the form, they cannot re-enter and change their answers.
 - Electronic administrations of the EKAN should be password protected whenever possible.
 - Access to the electronic form must be disabled immediately after administration sessions.
 - We encourage the use of commercially available survey software such as Qualtrics® for administering the EKAN. Under certain circumstances, we may be able provide individualized access to a study-specific Qualtrics® web portal where examinees can complete the EKAN (and demographic items). Raw data will then be provided back to the PI. Please contact Dr. Spurlock (dspurlock@mecn.edu) to discuss this option.
- The scoring key must be kept separately from the exam form at all times and secured on a password-protected computer.
- The scoring key must not be transmitted, transferred, or shared in any form (verbally, electronically, or on paper) with anyone outside the research team headed by the Principal Investigator (PI) who has signed this form.

EKAN Terms of Use

- Establishing robust validity, reliability and normative scoring information about new measures is essential to advancing the science of nursing education. Thus, EKAN users agree to share de-identified EKAN data with the EKAN authors within 180 days of administration of the EKAN. These data will be added to an aggregate database for the purpose of further validating and refining the EKAN (e.g., updating norms, assessing cross-national equivalence, etc.). EKAN users agree to provide the following:
 - For each use of the EKAN, a brief narrative description of the study purpose, design, participants, dates of data collection, primary language of examinees, and study setting (including City/State/Country).
 - For each use of the EKAN, the raw item responses and responses to demographic items, minimally age, gender, and primary language. Model demographic items are available from the EKAN authors.
 - Please send the raw data file in SPSS, Microsoft Excel, or CSV format to scale@nursingmeasure.org. Please include a key for coding categorical variables (gender, language, etc.).

Please utilize the following citation in any publication for the EKAN instrument until further notice:

Spurlock, D. & Wonder, A. (2015). Validity and reliability of a new objective measure: The Evidence-Based Practice Knowledge Assessment in Nursing (EKAN). *Journal of Nursing Education*, 54(11), 605-613.

I have read and agree to the terms of use for the EKAN instrument.

Name of Principal Investigator/EKAN User

5/31/16
Date

Name of Faculty Adviser (for student projects)

Date

Return electronically or via email to scale@nursingmeasure.org.

APPENDIX D

EKAN TOOL

The Evidence-Based Practice Knowledge Assessment in Nursing (EKAN)

<http://nursingmeasure.org>

EKAN Authors:

<p>Amy Hagedorn Wonder, PhD, RN School of Nursing Indiana University 1033 E. Third Street Sycamore Hall (Room 408) Bloomington, IN 47405 Phone Number: 812-855-1734 Fax Number: 812-855-6986 Home Phone Number: 812-630-2570 Email: awonder@iu.edu Other email: amycwonder@gmail.com</p>	<p>Darrell Spurlock, Jr. PhD, RN, NEA-BC, ANEF Mount Carmel College of Nursing 127 S. Davis Ave. Columbus, OH 43222 Phone Number: 614-234-5777 Fax Number: 614-547-8039 Cell Phone: 614-656-2202 Email: dspurlock@mccn.edu Other email: dspurlockjr@gmail.com</p>
---	---

The EKAN is the intellectual property of the EKAN authors and is protected by U.S. Copyright Law. The EKAN may be used only by permission of one of the EKAN authors.

To use this test form, you must have submitted a signed *EKAN Terms of Use* form to scale@nursingmeasure.org.

The 20-item EKAN was designed to measure EBP knowledge from across a wide range of EBP topics, framed by national competency frameworks from AACN and QSEN (see [Spurlock & Wonder, 2015](#) for more on the conceptual background of the EKAN). These competency frameworks outline the knowledge, skills, and attitudes students (or nurses) should possess, generally at the completion of their educational programs. Recognizing that competence (and the knowledge which underlies it) is developed over time, across courses, and with deliberate practice and repeated exposure, those wishing to use the EKAN to measure knowledge in relatively brief, pre-test/post-test designs may want to consider this as they select instruments for their projects.

The EKAN uses a simple scoring method (n correct/20). Scores should be reported for the whole instrument, not user-designated scales. The EKAN answer key may not be further distributed by EKAN users without EKAN author approval. The EKAN may not be used in high-stakes testing situations.

Users of the EKAN for research purposes agree to provide the EKAN authors with a de-identified dataset of subject responses to the EKAN items within 180 days of data collection. Responses should be recorded with the actual subject answers (e.g., #3: A), not simply a *correct/incorrect* indication for the item. When possible, demographic information should be provided, along with a key for coding of the data. These data are requested to assist in continued improvement and study of the EKAN.

The EKAN was designed as an objective knowledge measure. To maintain security over the items and to support continued validity, **the EKAN may not be distributed electronically for**

examinees to take outside a secure, face-to-face testing environment. This restriction includes the remote use of “secure testing browsers” at this time.

Instructions: Circle the best answer for each question below. If you are unsure of the answer, make your best guess. Systematic guessing or randomly answering questions is strongly discouraged.

1. You read a research study where researchers are interested in predicting whether or not a patient will fall based on several factors such as patient age, sedating medications, and mental status. You anticipate the researchers used which statistical technique?

- A) Analysis of Variance
- B) Regression
- C) z-test

2. Which approach is likely to produce the strongest evidence to guide practice?

- A) Subjects are interviewed in-depth using a structured interview guide
- B) Subjects randomly assigned to treatment groups
- C) Subjects studied as one treatment group with no comparison

3. What is the reason for obtaining approval from an Institutional Review Board (IRB) to conduct a study?

- A) HIPAA regulations require all research be approved by an IRB
- B) To ensure the study has substantial scientific merit
- C) To protect the rights of participants in the research study

4. What measure of central tendency reflects the most frequently occurring value in a distribution of data?

- A) Mean
- B) Median
- C) Mode

5. While critically appraising a research study, you evaluate whether an instrument accurately measures the concept it claims to measure. What measurement property are you evaluating?

- A) Applicability
- B) Reliability
- C) Validity

6. Which of the following resources is best to inform a point-of-care decision?

- A) Case studies
- B) Clinical practice guidelines
- C) Meta-analyses

7. Which of the following is most important when determining whether population-based evidence can be applied to an individual patient?

- A) Clinical judgment
- B) Generalizability
- C) Study sample size

8. What is the first step to enact evidence-based practice in nursing?

- A) Identify a problem in practice
- B) Identify barriers to change
- C) Seek leader approval for the change

9. Which of the following is most essential in facilitating an evidence-based change in practice?

- A) Educating nurses on the value of EBP
- B) Ensuring the presence of EBP mentor(s) in the practice setting
- C) More time for nurses to be involved in research

10. You read the following in a published systematic review: “Based on the results of the included studies ($N = 9$), a pooled effect size favoring the intervention was observed ($OR = 1.2$). Significant heterogeneity in effects among studies was observed ($OR = .7 - 2.1$).” Based on this information, what would you conclude?

- A) It is unclear if the intervention is effective or ineffective
- B) The intervention is consistently effective across studies
- C) The intervention is unlikely to be effective

11. Which of the following sources presents the least risk for bias?

- A) Meta-analysis from the Cochrane Database®
- B) Qualitative report located in CINAHL®
- C) Research report published by a pharmaceutical company

12. Within the PDSA cycle, what is the purpose of the “Act” stage?

- A) Disseminate findings in a journal article
- B) Evaluate findings, refine the change, repeat testing
- C) Seek and assess additional evidence to support a practice change

13. Which component of EBP determines the extent to which all other components will influence a treatment decision?

- A) Clinical expertise
- B) Research
- C) Patient values

14. You read the following statement in a journal article: “After accounting for covariates, body mass index (BMI) independently predicted low back pain scores ($R^2 = .42, p = .005$).” What is the most accurate interpretation of this statement?

- A) Being overweight (high BMI) causes low back pain.
- B) The relationship between low back pain and BMI was non-significant.
- C) There was a positive relationship between low back pain ratings and BMI.

15. Which of the following research designs provides the strongest evidence for nursing practice?

- A) Correlational
- B) Experimental
- C) Quasi-experimental

16. The oncology unit EBP committee is reviewing research articles as part of a practice change initiative. Several studies of the same intervention used different primary outcome measures. If all three are options, which measurement strategy represents the strongest, most trustworthy measurement approach?
- A) Biophysiologic measurements
 - B) Coded observations
 - C) Self-reports
17. When retrieving, appraising, and summarizing evidence, what step is essential in maintaining focus?
- A) Create a timeline
 - B) Formulate a PICOT question
 - C) Rewrite the research problem
18. Which of the following is an example of a nurse-sensitive quality indicator?
- A) Cardiac arrest survival rate
 - B) Patient fall rate
 - C) Stroke mortality rate
19. When reading a newly published research paper, you see the term, Cohen's *d*. What is Cohen's *d* a measure of?
- A) Central tendency
 - B) Effect size
 - C) Variability
20. Which of the following statements about statistical significance is true?
- A) Statistically significant findings are always clinically significant
 - B) Statistical significance is necessary for findings to be clinically significant
 - C) Statistical significance is not required for findings to be clinically significant

APPENDIX E

PERMISSION TO USE EBPSE SCALE

From: Kimberly Jordan - University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics [<mailto:noreply@qualtrics-survey.com>]
Sent: Monday, January 07, 2019 8:57 AM
To: Hall, Sandra
Subject: Permission to Use Evidence-Based Nursing Practice Self-Efficacy Scale (EXTERNAL EMAIL)

Children's Hospital Los Angeles

Thank you for your interest in the Evidence-Based Nursing Practice Self-Efficacy Scale developed by Sharon Tucker, PhD, RN; Marcelline Harris, PhD, RN; and Mariann E. Olson, PhD, RN. This tool may be useful for assessing nurses' confidence with EBP skills. Permission is granted as requested today, it is not granted for revising or modifying.

Following is a link to the scale and instructions for use. Cronbach coefficients ranged from .95 to .98. Average scores increased significantly ($p < .01$) following an evidence-based practice educational program. We ask that you share what you learned and submit your data for us to complete further psychometric evaluation. You are responsible for data management and analysis for use within your organization. Please format as an Excel file as follows with the questions across the top and the respondent number in the left column:

Respondent ID	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Etc through Q 17	Comments
1									
2 (etc)									

The number of the answer circled (or the comment) goes in the appropriate cell. Please email the Excel file to laura-cullen@uiowa.edu.

[Evidence-Based Nursing Practice Self Efficacy Scale](#)

Citation:

Tucker, S. J., Olson, M. E. & Frusti, D. K. (2009). Evidence-based practice self-efficacy scale: Preliminary reliability and validity. *Clinical Nurse Specialist*, 23(4), 207-215. doi:10.1097/NUR.0b013e3181aae8c6

Thank you for your interest. We are excited for the nursing community to use this scale. If you have any questions, please contact Laura Cullen at 319-384-9144 or laura-cullen@uiowa.edu.

APPENDIX F

EBPSE SCALE

EVIDENCE-BASED NURSING PRACTICE SELF-EFFICACY SCALE

Developed by Sharon J. Tucker, PhD, RN; Marcelline Harris, PhD, RN; Marianne E Olson, PhD, RN
Mayo Clinic- Department of Nursing – Rochester, Minnesota

Instructions:

The following items describe activities that support and ensure evidence-based nursing practice. Using a pen or pencil, for each of the 17 items below, rate how confident you are that you can do each activity listed using a number from 0 to 100. These numbers mean that you are not at all confident or sure (0%) to completely confident or sure (100%) that you can do each of these things listed. You can use the scale directly below to gauge your confidence from 0-100% and then put percentage in the space provided after each item.

PICK ONE OF THESE NUMBERS AND WRITE ON THE LINE NEXT TO EACH ITEM BELOW.

0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
Not confident			Moderately confident				Confident			

SELF-EFFICACY STEM

CONFIDENCE
MARK 0-100%

I am THIS PERCENT confident I can complete the following activities that support nursing practice:

- | | |
|-----|---|
| 1. | Routinely ask questions about my practice. _____ % |
| 2. | Locate resources in my department and institution to facilitate my understanding of research literature relevant to my nursing practice. _____ % |
| 3. | Locate resources in my department and institution necessary to institute an evidence-based practice change. _____ % |
| 4. | Locate and review published practice guidelines that support nursing interventions important to my practice. _____ % |
| 5. | Locate and review published research studies that have relevance to nursing interventions important to my practice. _____ % |
| 6. | Organize the necessary support and procedures to make a nursing practice change based on evidence (research, clinical practice guidelines, clinical expertise, patient goals/preferences). _____ % |
| 7. | Routinely identify patient outcomes to target nursing interventions. _____ % |
| 8. | Integrate the various sources of evidence and apply to my specialty population and practice. _____ % |
| 9. | Activate the processes to implement an evidence-based practice change. _____ % |
| 10. | Modify nursing interventions recommended for my patient population based on characteristics of the specific unit in which I work. _____ % |
| 11. | Routinely evaluate the research literature and other sources of evidence related to nursing interventions for my specialty population and practice. _____ % |
| 12. | Routinely implement nursing interventions that are supported by evidence (research and other sources such as practice guidelines) for my patient population and practice. _____ % |
| 13. | Modify nursing interventions I routinely implement based on what I learn about my patient's preferences. _____ % |
| 14. | Routinely modify nursing interventions based on outcomes and goals. _____ % |
| 15. | Routinely evaluate the effectiveness of nursing interventions using measurable outcomes. _____ % |
| 16. | Obtain proper training and education to be able to effectively implement an evidence-based nursing intervention or practice. _____ % |
| 17. | Implement an evidence-based nursing intervention individualized to my patient/family situation without losing the fidelity of the intervention (i.e., delivering as it was intended to be delivered). _____ % |

APPENDIX G

EBP FELLOWSHIP PROGRAM CURRICULUM

Evidence-Based Practice
Fellowship Curriculum

Month	Class Topics	Deliverables*
Month 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fellowship Intro and Overview Introduction to EBP and the Johns Hopkins Model Johns Hopkins Tools EBP Resources and Mentors Developing a Background Question Development of a PICO(T) Question Use of JH Question Development Tool Stakeholder Analysis Independent Work Time 	Completed Question Development Tool and Stakeholder Analysis Tool
Month 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Literature Search Strategies/CHLA's Databases and Health Sciences Library 1:1 feedback session for Question Development and Stakeholder Analysis Types of Evidence Overview/Levels of Evidence Quantitative Research Overview Basic Statistics Overview Independent Literature Search Time 	1-5 quantitative research articles related to EBP topic (goal to be set mutually between fellow and facilitator)
Month 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Qualitative Research Overview Non-Research Evidence Overview Internal Evidence Sources and Strategies Survey Design & Resources Independent Literature Search and Evidence Strategy Development 	Minimum 10 relevant pieces of evidence and internal evidence plan
Month 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Critical Appraisal of Research Critical Appraisal of Non-Research Evidence Summary Tool/TOE Independent Work on Critical Appraisals 	<p>Critical Appraisal Tools for all evidence</p> <p>Evidence Summary Tool</p> <p>Start recruiting project implementation team</p>

Month 5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evidence Synthesis Recommendation Development and Considerations Review EBP versus QI versus Research Action Planning and Resource Identification Stakeholder Review Process and Outcome Measures Independent Work- action planning, outcome identification 1:1 facilitator/fellow discussion about project progress and future plans 	<p>For translatable EBP projects: Action plan with measurable outcomes</p> <p>Implementation timeline</p> <p>For projects progressing to QI/Research: Meet with Quality Ambassador or Nurse Scientist to plan next steps</p> <p>For those moving into Scholars track: Meet with fellowship coordinator to create plan for Months 6-12</p>
Month 6	<p>No class- work independently</p> <p>Attend QI Workshop if moving to QI project</p> <p>Meet with Nurse Scientist if moving to research study</p> <p>Meet with EBP mentors to review timeline and begin implementation</p>	<p>EBP- Review timeline with mentor and begin implementation</p> <p>QI- Workshop completion and project timeline/outcomes</p> <p>Research- IRB application submission</p> <p>Scholars- Submit list of 3-5 topics for literature review</p> <p>All submit Project Progress Report</p>
Month 7	No class- work independently	Project Progress Report
Month 8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dissemination Options Writing Workshop Independent Work 	<p>Project Progress Report</p> <p>Written background, literature review, & methodology</p>
Month 9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creating Effective PowerPoints Designing Professional Posters Independent Work 	<p>Project Progress Report</p> <p>Abstract first draft</p> <p>Written challenges and future goals</p>
Month 10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1:1 Poster draft & abstract feedback Presentation Skills Workshop Independent Work 	<p>Project Progress Report</p> <p>Poster draft</p> <p>PowerPoint presentation</p> <p>Final abstract</p>

Evidence-Based Practice Fellowship Curriculum

Month 11	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Presentation Practice• Independent Work	Project Progress Report Final poster Final PowerPoint presentation Identification of at least one journal or conference for abstract submission
Month 12	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Presentations and Poster Session	Complete submission of abstract to conference or journal

APPENDIX H

EBP FELLOWSHIP CURRICULUM OUTCOMES

Evidence-Based Practice Fellowship Curriculum Outcomes

Fellowship Introduction & Overview	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss program expectations, timeline, deadlines, and deliverables
Introduction to EBP and the Johns Hopkins Model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define evidence-based practice • Discuss the importance of EBP in health care • Identify the difference between EBP, quality improvement, and research
Johns Hopkins Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify tools available for use in EBP projects • Discuss where to find tools in CHLA intranet
EBP Resources & Mentors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss need for mentorship • Identify a mentor for EBP project • Describe available EBP resources at CHLA and how to access them
Developing Background Question	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify the purpose of a background question • Formulate a background question
Development of a PICO(T) Question	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify the components of a PICO(T) question • Create a PICO(T) question
Use of the Johns Hopkins Question Development Tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss components of the Question Development Tool • Identify responses for prompts within the Question Development Tool
Stakeholder Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss the importance of involving stakeholders in EBP • Identify interprofessional stakeholders for project

Evidence-Based Practice Fellowship Curriculum Outcomes

Literature Search Strategies/CHLA's Databases and Health Sciences Library	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify CHLA databases and free resources • Describe how to request articles through interlibrary loan • Discuss search strategies and techniques for refining and limiting searches
Types of Evidence Overview/Levels of Evidence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify the difference between research and non-research evidence • Describe research and non-research evidence within the context of the Johns Hopkins levels of evidence
Quantitative Research Overview	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify key components of quantitative research • Describe the difference between an independent variable and a dependent variable • Discuss the significance of concepts such as randomization, control, sample, and setting • Describe factors to consider when evaluating research for translation into practice
Basic Statistics Overview	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss how sample size affects reliability of results • Describe how to assess for statistical significance in research study results • Discuss the implications of odds ratios in understanding research statistics

Qualitative Research Overview	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the differences between qualitative and quantitative research Discuss considerations for transferability of qualitative research findings
Non-Research Evidence Overview	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify the types of non-research evidence that may inform an EBP project Discuss concepts related to generalizability and transferability of non-research evidence
Internal Evidence Sources and Strategies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify the types of internal evidence available at CHLA Discuss sources of internal evidence Describe how internal evidence contributes to the EBP process
Survey Design and Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify key considerations for survey development Demonstrate use of Redcap system for survey design and management
Critical Appraisal of Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstrate understanding of key concepts surrounding evidence appraisal, including sample size, study design, instrument reliability and validity, and statistical analysis Identify the level and quality of a research study using the Johns Hopkins Research Evidence Appraisal Tool

Evidence-Based Practice Fellowship Curriculum Outcomes

Critical Appraisal of Non-Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify type of non-research evidence as categorized by Johns Hopkins • Discuss key components for appraisal of evidence • Identify the level and quality of evidence using the non-research evidence using the Johns Hopkins Non-Research Evidence Appraisal Tool
Evidence Summary Tool/Table of Evidence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explain the importance of organizing and summarizing evidence in EBP • Discuss the key components of a table of evidence • Complete the Johns Hopkins Evidence Summary Tool
Evidence Synthesis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss the possible conclusions to be reached following evidence appraisal • Demonstrate the use of the Johns Hopkins Evidence Synthesis Tool • Synthesize evidence to identify a final recommendation for EBP project
Recommendation and Development Considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe factors that affect feasibility of evidence translation, including organizational/financial considerations and patient and family preferences • Explain risks versus benefits for EBP project translation

Review EBP vs QI vs Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the purpose of and methodologies used in EBP, QI, and research Analyze evidence synthesis to determine next steps for EBP project, including full translation, pilot translation, research, and quality improvement
Action Planning and Resource Identification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discuss key components of action plan development Identify potential barriers to project completion Develop a timeline for project completion Determine necessary resources for project completion
Stakeholder Review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe the need for stakeholder communication and buy-in prior to project translation Analyze Stakeholder Identification Tool to determine whether updates are needed
Process and Outcomes Measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define process measures Define outcome measures Define balancing measures Discuss the importance of measuring outcomes to determine project success Identify outcomes to be measured for project
Dissemination Options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Discuss the importance of disseminating work Describe methods of dissemination

Evidence-Based Practice Fellowship Curriculum Outcomes

Writing Workshop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss the process for submitting a manuscript for publication • Describe key components to include in a manuscript • Demonstrate use of APA format in writing • Identify writing mentor/editor for manuscript development
Creating Effective PowerPoints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss the use of PowerPoint to accompany spoken presentations • Describe appropriate slide design and layout, including text and color considerations
Designing Professional Posters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify the purpose of professional posters • Discuss the key elements that should be included in a professional poster • Describe key poster design concepts and resources for graphic elements of posters • Analyze sample posters to identify opportunities for improvement
Presentation Skills Workshop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discuss key considerations for developing public speaking skills • Develop short presentation about project and practice delivery

APPENDIX I

EBP FELLOWSHIP PROGRAM GUIDELINES

EBP Fellowship Program Guidelines

Purpose: The purpose of this program is to provide nurses at Children's Hospital Los Angeles with the knowledge and resources necessary to engage in evidence-based practice (EBP) in their daily work. Participants will conduct a full evidence-based practice project.

Format: The EBP Fellowship Program is a year-long program comprised of both class time and independent work time. Selected participants will attend one 6-hour class day per month and will have an additional 6 hours per month of dedicated paid time to work on their projects.

Eligibility: The EBP Fellowship Program is open to all CHLA nurses who have worked as an RN for at least 18 consecutive months.

Application: Those interested should complete an application and submit it no later than the due date. The application consists of a short form, one short essay, and a letter of recommendation from the applicant's manager. The manager letter of recommendation must specify that the manager understands the time commitment and will support the applicant to participate.

Participant Expectations:

- Commit to participating as a fellow for one year
- Attend all scheduled classes
- Complete and submit all assignments/deliverables on time
- Maintain an up-to-date project management guide
- Communicate any challenges or needs to the program facilitator as soon as possible

Project Completion: Following Month 5 of the program, participants will determine whether sufficient evidence exists to translate a new intervention into nursing practice at CHLA. For those who are unable to move into translation due to a lack of evidence or resources, several alternative options will be made available, including participation in research, quality improvement, and additional EBP work on another topic. The program facilitator will work with each fellow to ensure that they are able to engage in meaningful EBP work throughout the full year of the fellowship.

Dissemination: All participants will be expected to disseminate their work at the end of the fellowship program. This must take the form of a professional poster and oral presentation using PowerPoint at a fellowship dissemination event to take place in the final month of the program. Additional support will be made available to assist with submitting abstracts for conferences and/or manuscript for publication.

Questions regarding the EBP Fellowship Program should be directed to:
Sandy Hall, MSN, MBA, RN-BC, NE-BC
Manager, Nursing Excellence
sahall@chla.usc.edu
323-361-5374

APPENDIX J

EBP FELLOWSHIP APPLICATION

EBP Fellowship
Application

Name: _____

Title/Position: _____

Department: _____

Manager's Name: _____

Years of experience in current role: _____

Topic of Interest: _____

Previous experience with EBP: _____

Please submit the following items:

- Signed application
- Short (500 words or less) essay about your topic of interest, population affected, and potential impact of your project
- Letter of support from manager (see template)

Participation in CHLA's EBP Fellowship is a paid experience with the goal of completing an EBP project. Participation requires attending all scheduled classes, as well as independent work time outside of class. Opportunities will be granted to support projects that lead to research or quality improvement if needed. I understand that I will be paid for my time in the fellowship and time spent working on projects, and I agree to accurately account for time spent on my project.

Signed: _____

Date: _____

APPENDIX K

EBP FELLOWSHIP APPLICATION SCORING RUBRIC

EBP Fellowship Application Scoring Rubric
--

Applicant Name: _____

Reviewer Name: _____

Date: _____

Please consider the following components of the application, and provide a score in the box provided. Each category should be scored from 0-10, with 0= poor and 10= excellent.

Potential Impact: What is the potential for an EBP project about this topic to improve patient outcomes or satisfaction, patient quality of life, or nurse satisfaction?	Score (0-10):
Feasibility: How likely is it that the applicant will be successful in completing this project?	Score (0-10):
Writing Skill: How well are the short essay answers written? Does the applicant have a basic mastery of sentence construction, grammar, and spelling?	Score (0-10):
Appropriate for EBP: Does current research exist about this topic? If not, is there potential for either a QI or research project if sufficient existing evidence does not support translation into practice?	Score (0-10):
Likelihood of Program Completion: Does the applicant seem dedicated to participating in and completing the fellowship program? Any concerns that they will not meet the one-year commitment?	Score (0-10):
Leadership Support: Did the applicant include a letter of support from their manager? (Score 0 if not.) Does the manager indicate willingness to support the applicant with assistance in scheduling to ensure attendance at all fellowship classes?	Score (0-10):
Total Score	

Please return to Sandy Hall, MS #74, no later than May 15, 2019.

APPENDIX L

EBP FELLOWSHIP PROJECT PROGRESS REPORT

EBP Fellowship
Project Progress Report

Fellowship Month: _____

Name: _____

Department: _____

Project Title/Topic: _____

Current project status: _____

Challenges: _____

New ideas/concepts learned or applied this month: _____

Have you met with your mentor in the last month? Yes No

Are you currently up to date with your project timeline? Yes No

What, if any, additional support do you need? _____